

RDA National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist

RDA Recommendation

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Abstract: The National PID Strategies Working Group was endorsed to explore how Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) form part of national policy and research infrastructure implementation frameworks. The Group recognises that there are systemic and network benefits from widespread and consistent PID adoption including financial and time savings benefits. Research sector stakeholders including funders, government agencies, and national research communities have created PID consortia or policies (including mandates) in pursuit of these benefits. At the establishment of the WG, National PID Strategies were beginning to emerge in the UK, Australia, the Netherlands, and Canada as a pathway to realising these benefits and an international conversation felt needed. RDA provided an umbrella for discussion and alignment between the strategies, refinement of the value proposition and sharing practical development pathways to a national PID strategy.

Impact: The RDA National PID Strategies WG has produced a comparison guide and checklist that can be used when developing a national PID strategy. This is supported by the nine case studies collected from countries at different stages of developing a national PID strategy. The countries are Australia, Canada, Czech Republic, Finland, Germany, the Netherlands, New Zealand, South Korea, and the United Kingdom.

The guide offers a comparison of the nine case studies, including scope, drivers, strategy development, key features and priority PIDs. The checklist can be used as a starting point for developing your national PID strategy. You do not need to complete all of the numbered points or follow the order. The checklist is designed to be used flexibly to help you think about what is needed.

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RDA webpage: <https://rd-alliance.org/group/national-pid-strategies-wg/outcomes/rda-national-pid-strategies-guide-and-checklist>

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Pathways to National PID Strategies

Guide and Checklist to facilitate uptake and alignment

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Introduction to the Guide

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) National PID Strategies Working Group (WG) was endorsed by RDA on 10 December 2021 to explore how Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) form part of national policy and research infrastructure implementation frameworks. The Group recognises that there are systemic and network benefits from widespread and consistent PID adoption including financial and time savings benefits. Research sector stakeholders including funders, government agencies, and national research communities have created PID consortia or policies (including mandates) in pursuit of these benefits. At the establishment of the WG, National PID Strategies were beginning to emerge in the UK, Australia, the Netherlands, and Canada as a pathway to realising these benefits and an international conversation felt needed. RDA provided an umbrella for discussion and alignment between the strategies, refinement of the value proposition and sharing practical development pathways to a national PID strategy.

The findings of the 18 months of the WG (December 2021 - June 2023) have been that:

1. National PID Strategies are on the rise, evidenced in the case studies collected by the WG and the growing momentum of discussions at RDA Plenaries and other international fora.
2. The development of National PID Strategies is a relatively new phenomenon and many countries are in the very early stages. In fact, many have more of a national approach that they are seeking to transform into a strategy.
3. All national PID strategies are currently in development and therefore subject to a high degree of change. During the course of the WG, nine case studies were collected and several of these needed to be updated prior to the Group's final output due to changes that had taken place in those countries.
4. There is no single 'cookie cutter' approach to developing a national PID strategy. Critical components include:
 - A clear value proposition with use cases
 - A group or organisation that is responsible for driving strategy development
 - An open, inclusive, iterative process that involves all stakeholders
 - An accompanying roadmap that outlines practical steps for implementation
5. International PID providers such as ORCID and DataCite have begun to actively engage with national PID strategies and the RDA National PID Strategies WG provides a focal point for furthering this engagement.

An ambitious goal of the WG was to map common activities and produce a guide to help others - irrespective of geographical region - to follow a 'blueprint' to define their national PID strategy. However, given the findings listed above, a 'blueprint Guide' to national PID strategies is not possible at this stage. Instead, we provide a Guide that compares and contrasts national PID strategies based on nine case studies we have collected. A National PID Strategy Checklist is also included to summarise and highlight key considerations.

Key messages

Summary of the key messages from the RDA National PID Strategies WG:

1. National PID Strategies are on the rise
2. There is no single 'cookie cutter' approach to developing a national PID strategy
3. Critical components include:
 - A clear value proposition with use cases

- A group or organisation that is responsible for driving strategy development
 - An open, inclusive, iterative process that involves all stakeholders
 - An accompanying roadmap that outlines practical steps for implementation
4. Engagement between national PID strategies and PID providers is important for success

The RDA National PID Strategies WG has produced a comparison guide and checklist that can be used when developing a national PID strategy.

Case studies

This Guide, to facilitate uptake and alignment of National PID Strategies, is based on comparing and contrasting case studies.

Method

Submissions of case studies were requested through an open call for anyone to submit using the template developed by co-chairs and reviewed, adjusted and approved at WG meetings. The open call for case studies submission was made repeatedly throughout the duration of the Working Group via email to the WG members list, at RDA Plenary WG sessions and at WG meetings held between plenaries. Disappointingly, some presentations given at WG meetings or Plenary sessions were not subsequently received as case studies and could not be included in this Guide. Other than completing the template, there were no eligibility criteria for submitting a case study and no case studies were modified or rejected by co-chairs or the WG. The case study template has been included in this Guide.

Note: we welcome additional case studies from anyone in any country or region to be submitted to the recently established [National PID Strategies IG](#), who will be responsible for care and further development of this Guide and Checklist.

As a result of this open call process, we received case studies from the following countries and regions:

1. Australia
2. Canada
3. Czech Republic
4. Finland
5. Germany
6. Korea
7. New Zealand
8. The Netherlands
9. United Kingdom

Case studies were collected via the WG and included sections on:

- Lead organisations
- Scope
- Drivers
- Strategy development
- Key features
- Key infrastructure
- Priority PIDs
- Impact and monitoring

Case studies are included with the Guide.

How to use the Guide and Checklist

You can use the Guide, Case Studies and Checklist developed by the RDA National PID Strategies WG to:

- Inform the development of your National PID Strategy
- Develop a roadmap to accompany your strategy
- Align with international initiatives in this important area
- Facilitate stakeholder engagement with National PID Strategies
- Connect, communicate and collaborate with others developing National PID Strategies

The Guide

Lead organisation

Summary: A critical component in developing a National PID Strategy or approach is to have a group or organisation that is responsible for driving strategy development. The lead is responsible for a variety of tasks such as: initiating the Strategy discussion; developing/refining the value proposition; bringing stakeholders together; coordinating events; coordinating input mechanisms such as focus groups; providing financial support for Strategy development; stakeholder communication; coordinating and/or drafting the Strategy itself.

Comparison table

Country or region	Lead organisation(s)
Australia	Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC): 1. National PID Strategy Taskforce
Canada	Canadian Research Knowledge Network (CRKN) Canadian PID Advisory Committee (CPIDAC): 1. ORCID-CA Governing Committee (OCGC) 2. DataCite Canada Governing Committee (DCCGC) Digital Research Alliance of Canada (The Alliance)
Czech Republic	National Library of Technology
Finland	CSC – IT Center for Science <ul style="list-style-type: none">• DataCite Finland Consortium lead• ORCID Consortium Coordinator• ePIC Consortium member National Library of Finland <ul style="list-style-type: none">• URN service provider• Finnish ISBN, ISNI and ISSN Agencies National Land Survey <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Geodata identifiers Digital and Population Data Services Agency

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government interoperability service provider Natural History Museum/University of Helsinki <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GBIF partner
Germany	DataCite German National Library (DNB) Helmholtz Open Science Office, Helmholtz Association German National Library of Science and Technology (TIB) Bielefeld University Library
Korea	Korea Institute of Science and Technology Information (KISTI)
New Zealand	The overarching strategy was derived as a consequence of the <i>2016 Research, Science and Innovation Domain Plan</i> which was developed in a process led by: Ministry of Business, Innovation and Employment (MBIE) Statistics New Zealand Ministry of Education Tertiary Education Commission
The Netherlands	NWO DANS-KNAW UKB SURF CWTS-Leiden University
United Kingdom	Jisc UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Research England

Scope

Summary: Defining the scope of the Strategy (i.e. who it applies to) is important but is not always clear at the beginning of Strategy development and may evolve during the process. The scope of a national PID strategy varies between countries but common elements include research and government data. The Strategy may apply to the entire national research, government and innovation system. For some, an accompanying Roadmap will also be developed to ensure that the Strategy is acted upon. While the Strategy focuses on high level goals and a shared vision, the Roadmap defines the ‘who, what, when and how’ needed to achieve the Strategy.

Stakeholders

Summary: While a specific question on identifying stakeholders in a National PID Strategy was not included in the Case Study template, discussion within the RDA National PID Strategies WG has raised this common need. Involvement of key stakeholders are varied and include a selection of:

- PID service providers
- PID consortia
- research infrastructure and service providers
- organisations, groups or networks that advance FAIR and open research
- research funding bodies
- institutions and universities
- researchers
- research stewards
- research publishers
- government

Example: Czech Republic Case Study

Target institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Public research performing organisations (RPOs): Higher Education Institutions and Research organisations ● Research funding organisations (RFOs): Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports, Czech Science Foundation, Technology Agency of the Czech Republic etc. ● Policymakers: Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports; Research, Development and Innovation Council (R&D&I Council) ● Libraries: National library, National Library of Technology, academic libraries ● Publishers based in Czechia ● Service providers, research infrastructures
Target groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researchers ● Librarians ● Open Science/Open Access managers/coordinators ● CRIS system managers ● Repository managers ● Other research support positions, e.g. data stewards, data curators

Drivers for a national PID strategy (value proposition)

Summary: Common drivers between the case studies collected include:

- National coordination, consolidation and alignment of PID investment
- Lower cost and barriers to PID adoption
- Reduce administrative burden
- Enable research to be more FAIR and Open
- Improve linking and discovery of research outputs and entities
- Improve systems interoperability
- Better research reporting including for national research assessment exercises (such as UK REF reporting)
- Better tracking of research outcomes and impact
- Support best practice

Additional and unique-to-country drivers include:

- Develop the digital research infrastructure of the future (Canada)
- Reproducibility (Finland and the Netherlands)
- Build national services to support interoperability (Finland)
- Better curation of research outputs and correct author attribution (Korea)
- Responsible management of research information (Netherlands)
- Coordinated networking and promotion of PID systems (Germany)
- A formal framework for management and access to PIDs and introduce them as a standard into the Czech R&D environment (Czech Republic)
- Enact goals of the 2021 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap (Australia)

National Strategies often need to present the value proposition for PID investment and national coordination via a combination of the drivers above, including how PID adoption supports sector-wide policy objectives (e.g. providing world class data infrastructure, maintaining competitive advantage, making research more FAIR and Open, etc.).

Strategy development

Most countries/regions are in the early phases of developing a national PID strategy. A common feature is that they are not starting at ground zero. In many cases, the development of a national strategy is evolving from pre-existing PID or research infrastructure governance groups such as Finland’s PID Forum Network or the Netherlands PID Advisory Group. They build on existing national PID services such as those offered via ORCID or DOI consortia or national PID providers such as Australia’s ARDC.

Roadmaps are a common feature of national PID strategies as they identify key stakeholders and provide a high-level action plan for getting from start to finish. Getting to a final agreed-upon roadmap may be a long and thorough process. For example, the UK produced 'Developing a persistent identifier roadmap for open access to UK research', which first proposed the outline of a national PID strategy; in the Netherlands a working group of the PID Advisory Board first produced a document called 'towards a national PID roadmap'; Canada’s approach was to develop a “roadmap to a roadmap” – “...helping the Canadian PID community to identify the necessary actions, initiatives, and stakeholders that must be in place and on board to ensure the successful development and implementation of an eventual PID Strategy for Canada.” Germany has a DFG funded project “PID Network Germany – Network for fostering persistent identifiers in science and culture” to produce a PID roadmap by the beginning of 2026.

Key features

Key features of national PID approaches/strategies according to the case studies collected to date include:

Feature	Description	Example(s)
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Lead organisation(s) or Group	Coordination and collaboration between key organisations, groups, networks. One or more 'responsible organisations' to drive the strategy forward. Coordination facilitated via national level coordination or advisory group to champion and guide the development and implementation of a national strategy.	See table under Lead Organisation section
Working group	Working group that is the forum for advancing the practical aspects of a national strategy	UK Research Identifier National Coordinating Committee (RINCC) https://rincc.org.uk/ Australian National PID Strategy Working Groups on topics: grants; projects; organisations and facilities etc.
Value proposition	Analysis and report to provide evidence and inform strategy.	Landscape analysis (Canada, UK, Germany) PID cost-benefit analysis (UK, Australia)
Funding	One or more organisations who provide funding such as to conduct an analysis report or run workshops.	Jisc & UKRI (UK) The Alliance and collaborators (Canada) ARDC & AAF (Australia) German Research Foundation (DFG) (Germany)

Stakeholders	<p>Involvement of key stakeholders are varied but include a selection of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PID service providers ● PID consortia ● research infrastructure and service providers ● organisations, groups or networks that advance FAIR and open research ● research funding bodies ● institutions and universities ● researchers ● research stewards ● research publishers ● government 	See Stakeholders section
Open process	An open, consultative and inclusive process to develop the strategy and roadmap was referenced in the majority of case studies.	Canada, UK, Australia, Finland, the Netherlands and Germany
Policy or position paper	A single organisation, a collaboration between organisations that has issued a PID policy of national scope.	Canada's position paper , Australia ARDC PID policy
Roadmap	Having a roadmap to take the national PID vision from A to B.	Finland, UK , Germany, Canada, Netherlands Towards a National PID Roadmap

Key infrastructure

Summary: Key infrastructure needed to support or engage with National PID Strategies varies between case studies. Common elements include:

- National research publication / discovery portal
- Repository / repositories
- International PID providers (e.g. ORCID)

Key infrastructure comparison table

Case study	Name of infrastructure	Key purpose
Finland	Fairdata.fi	Research data publication, metadata hub and preservation service
	Research.fi	National research information hub.
	National Library	Semantic artefacts, publications
	National interoperability services (?)	Semantic artefacts
The Netherlands	SURFrepository	Repository
	ISAAC	Grant applications
	NARCIS	National Academic Research and Collaborations Information System
	Pure	CRIS
	Converis	CRIS
	Metis	CRIS
Canada *in early stages of thinking this through	OJS	Open Publishing Platform
	DSpace	Digital Repository
UK	UK ORCID Consortium	Jisc is the lead organisation for this service providing reduced cost and support for its members
	DataCite Consortium	The British Library is the UK consortium and works with organisations in the UK and Ireland to ensure that their data, software and other research items can be uniquely identified with DOIs
	RAiD	A Persistent Identifier for research projects. Plans for a Registration Agency in the UK with the Registration Authority run by the Australian Research Data Commons
	UKRI New Funding Service (replacing Je-S from January 2024)	Grant application service
Korea (KISTI)	Korea DOI Center	Issuing DOIs to Korean research outputs, Intellectual properties, research data
	KISTI's experimental	Interlinking (literature, author, data) elements

	comprehensive identifier testbed (in progress)	with identifiers in Korean scholarly articles.
Australia	ARDC Identifier Services ARDC DataCite DOI Consortium Global RAiD Registration Authority	ARDC provides a range of services for research organisations to create and manage persistent identifiers (PIDs).
	AAF Australian ORCID Consortium	Australia's ORCID Consortium led by the Australian Access Federation (AAF)
	ARDC Data Discovery portals including Research Data Australia , Research Vocabularies Australia , Research Link Australia , Research Grants Australia	Discovery of research data and related materials
	ARC & NHMRC Grant opportunities portal	Research grant applications
	Institutional and discipline repositories	Storing, describing, sharing research outputs
	Government data repositories and portals (various)	Storing, describing, sharing government data
Germany	DataCite Consortium & ORCID Germany Consortium	TIB is the lead organisation for both services. This will definitely take into account when creating the PID roadmap for Germany
	German national bibliography https://www.dnb.de/EN/Professionell/Metadatendienst/Metadaten/Nationalbibliografie/nationalbibliografie_node.html	The aim is to offer stable and reliable bridges for the construction of a knowledge graph of culture and science
	Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE) https://www.base-search.net/?l=en	Since 2004, Bielefeld University Library has been productively developing and operating the scientific search engine BASE with the aim of indexing OA content from publication infrastructures, especially repositories, as comprehensively as possible.
Czech Republic	e-infra	This large infrastructure will build the National Repository Platform in the upcoming years. That should greatly facilitate adoption of PIDs.

	National CRIS - IS VaVal (R&D Information System)	National research information system. We plan on working with Research, Development and Innovation Council (in charge of IS VaVal) on integrating global PIDs into their submission processes as required. Nowadays it uses mostly local identifiers.
	Institutional CRIS systems	Various institutional CRIS systems at Czech RPOs. OBD (Personal Bibliographic Database) application is an outstanding case of an institutional CRIS system in the Czech Republic developed locally by a Czech company DERS. An ORCID integration for OBD is currently in development.
	Institutional or subject repositories	There are several repositories in the Czech republic collecting different objects, some are already using PIDs but there is still enough room to improve and really integrate those PIDs, not only allow their evidence.
	Major research funders	Grant application processes
	Local publishers	Content submission processes
New Zealand	NZ ORCID Hub https://orcidhub.org.nz/	Lower burdens of integration to enable all publicly funded NZ research organisations to participate
	DataCite tools and infrastructure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fabrica Web interface https://doi.datacite.org/ REST APIs https://support.datacite.org/docs/api 	Creation and management of DOIs; integration with data repository infrastructure; retrieve, query and browse DataCite DOI metadata records
	The New Zealand Research Information System (NZRIS) https://www.mbie.govt.nz/science-and-technology/science-and-innovation/research-and-data/nzris/	NZRIS will hold information about research funding and activity in New Zealand.

PIDs

Summary: Many National PID Strategies are taking the approach of looking at use cases: a description of the problem statement and how particular PIDs could address the problem. Common use cases for PIDs include:

- People - researchers, contributors

- Organisations - institutions, facilities, departments, groups, centres
- Research outputs - articles, data
- Funding - grants
- Projects and activities
- Samples, observations, instruments, specimens

Common to all of the nine case studies are the following PIDs types:

- ORCID
- DOI
- ROR

RAiD was the next most common PID type featured in five of the nine case studies (Finland, Netherlands, UK, Germany and Australia). There is a long tail of PIDs including IGSN, ISBN, RRID, ARK, Handle and more.

PIDs comparison table

Case study	Function	PID type
Finland	Researchers, persons	ORCID; ISNI
	Organisations	VAT-number (not resolvable yet) RoR ISNI PIC (not resolvable yet) SF-edu-ID (not resolvable yet)
	Funding decisions	URN
	Publications	CrossRef DOI, URN JuFo-id - Publication Forum publication channel ID (en) ISSN ISBN PMID
	Datasets	DataCite DOI, URN
	Specimens	doi
	Infrastructures	URN
	Concepts, data types	PURL, URN, URI, QID
	Research Activity	RAiD
The Netherlands	Identification of researcher(s) for funding and reporting	ORCID
	Identification of research output for reporting	DOI, URN, ISSN, Handle

	Identification of organisation	RoR, ISNI
	Identification of research grants	CrossRef DOI/GrantID
	Identification of research project	RAiD
	Identification of data set	Handle, DOI
	Identification of researcher(s) for findability research output	ORCID, ISNI or DAI
	Identification of research software	DOI, SWHID
	Identification of instruments	DOI, Handle, RRID, UID
	Identification of samples	IGSN, ARK, URN, HTTP URI (CETAF URI), DOI, UUID, RRID, BioSample accession number
Canada	Existing consortia support	ORCID
	Existing consortia support	DataCite DOI
	Considering use case for centralised support	Crossref DOI
	Considering use case for centralised support	ROR
UK	People	ORCID iDs
	Outputs	Crossref and DataCite DOIs
	Grants	Crossref DOIs
	Organisations	ROR (Research Organization Registry) identifiers
	Projects	RAiDs (Research Activity iDs)
Korea (KISTI)	Korean R&D outputs management	DOI (literature and data), Korean research funding ID, Korean national research ID
	Issuing DOIs to Korean research outputs, Intellectual properties, research data	DOI, ISNI, ORCID, ROR, WoS and SCOPUS author ID, Korean national author ID
Australia	Research grants	PURL or DOI
	Research outputs - articles, data, software and related materials	DOI
	Researchers, contributors	ORCID

	Research projects	RAiD
	Research instruments	DOI, Handle
	Samples and specimens	IGSN, DOI
	Research organisations	ROR
Germany	Research data	DataCite DOI, URN
	Instruments	DataCite DOI
	Academic Conferences	DataCite DOI GND (The Integrated Authority File) ID
	The persistent identification of cultural objects, holdings and collections and their contexts (associated events, actors, concepts) in the context of Humanities	GND ID
	Organisations & Projects	ROR GND ID GepriS Crossref Funder Registry RAiD
	Persons	ORCID GND ID
	Physical Objects	RRID IGSN
	PIDs for open access publication services and research information systems	No standard established at the moment
	Software	No standard established at the moment
	Text publication	Crossref & DataCite DOI URN
Czech Republic	Identification of researchers	ORCID
	Identification of research outputs	DOI (DataCite, CrossRef)
	Identification of organisations	ROR
	Identification of books	ISBN

	Identification of serial publications	ISSN
	Identification of printed music	ISMN
New Zealand	Deduplication of researchers Linkage with awards Authoritative attribution of affiliation and works	ORCID iD
	Identification of datasets, software and other types of research outputs	DataCite DOI
	Identification of organisations	GRID/ROR
	Identification of organisations in NZRIS	NZBN

Impact and monitoring

Summary: In most cases specific impact and monitoring activities have not yet been defined.

Example: Korea case study

KISTI's curation activities are reported and monitored to the Korean Ministry of Science and Technology. KISTI plans new research projects every 3 years in all divisions. It affects even essential infrastructure works (e.g., DOI RA management)

KISTI's current key concern is to accurately identify literature, authors, institutions, references and interlink them well. In this context, one of DOI RA's roles is to track the impact of Korean research outputs. (We named it as "Comprehensive interlinking identifiers")

Example: UK case study

The UK listed the impact of the work done to establish a national PID strategy as:

- Better understanding of the state of the art and best practice in the governance and delivery of PID services
- Increased awareness of persistent identifiers across the research sector
- Five validated priority PIDs selected through community consultation - outputs (DOIs), grants (Crossref Grant ID), people (ORCID), project (RAiD), organisations (ROR)
- Address inefficiencies and administrative burden in Open Access and publication workflows

Example: Czech Republic case study

The Czech National Library of Technology will deliver a cost-benefit analysis in two phases - in 2024 and 2028 (funded by project CARDS). The first phase will capture the current status of the selected PIDs usage within the Czech R&D environment and potential financial benefits of their effective implementation. The second phase will capture the progress in use of PIDs from 2024.

We will also set up regular monitoring of progress regarding adoption of ORCID, DOI (and other priority PIDs) with a set of identified key metrics as part of the National PID Centre impact assessment. There is also a monitoring mechanism embedded in the CARDS project.

Summary

National PID Strategies are on the rise. We anticipate rapid evolution of the nature and number of these strategies in the near future. You can use the Guide, Case Studies and Checklist developed by the RDA National PID Strategies WG to:

- Inform the development of your National PID Strategy
- Develop a roadmap to accompany your strategy
- Align with international initiatives in this important area
- Facilitate stakeholder engagement with National PID Strategies
- Connect, communicate and collaborate with others developing National PID Strategies

The RDA National PID Strategies Working Group is evolving into the RDA [National PID Strategies Interest Group](#). Please join this Interest Group to receive notices about upcoming meetings, new case studies and participate in this energetic community of practice.

National PID Strategy Checklist

Instructions: National PID Strategies are on the rise but there is no single ‘cookie cutter’ approach to developing one. Use this checklist as a guide to starting and/or developing your national PID strategy. You do not need to complete all of the numbered points or follow the order. The checklist is designed to be used flexibly to help you think about what is needed. Simply choose which of the questions apply.

Number	Checklist
1	<p>Have you established a clear value proposition for developing a national PID strategy? Does it speak to all stakeholders?</p> <p>Tip: Leverage existing value propositions such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Brown, Josh, Jones, Phill, Meadows, Alice, & Murphy, Fiona. (2022). Incentives to invest in identifiers: A cost-benefit analysis of persistent identifiers in Australian research systems. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7100578 ● Brown, Josh, Jones, Phill, Meadows, Alice, Murphy, Fiona, & Clayton, Paul. (2021). UK PID Consortium: Cost-Benefit Analysis (1.0). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4772627 ● Lisa Goddard, 2021. "Persistent Identifiers as Open Research Infrastructure to Reduce Administrative Burden." Pop! Public. Open. Participatory. no. 3. https://doi.org/10.54590/pop.2021.006.
2	<p>Have you identified your stakeholders (including their roles and responsibilities) and your approach to engaging them in the development of your strategy?</p> <p>Tip: conduct a landscape and stakeholder analysis; consider diversity, openness and inclusivity - how will you involve all stakeholders who want to be involved at the time they want to be involved?</p> <p>Stakeholders may include (but are not limited to):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researchers ● Publishers ● PID providers ● Research infrastructure providers ● Universities ● Research institutions ● Government ● Research funders
3	<p>Have you developed use cases that support the strategy?</p>
4	<p>Have you established who (person, group) will take responsibility for coordinating (driving) strategy development?</p> <p>Tip: Involve key stakeholders across multiple sectors in a coordination group.</p>
5	<p>Have you considered the scope/coverage and/or system boundaries of the</p>

	strategy?
6	<p>Have you considered developing a roadmap to accompany your strategy? A roadmap can identify practical steps including roles and responsibilities of stakeholders and a timeline to implement the strategy.</p> <p>Tip: Identify steps for what needs to happen, what infrastructure is required, who is going to do it, how it is going to be funded (where applicable), when it needs to be done, plus any risks or dependencies.</p>
7	<p>Have you developed a vision for what the strategy will deliver and by when?</p> <p>Tip: Involve your stakeholders in a visioning exercise.</p>
8	Have you secured funds needed to develop the strategy e.g. to run workshops?
9	Have you established an open, consultative and inclusive process to develop the strategy and/or roadmap? Will this be an iterative process with plenty of opportunities for feedback and adjustment?
10	Have you considered establishing working groups for stakeholders to explore different aspects of the strategy and include their outputs in strategy development?
11	<p>Have you considered the mechanism by which submissions can be made into the strategy and/or roadmap?</p> <p>Tip: you may want to design a different submission form for general submission and another for working group submission</p>
12	<p>Have you developed key messages and a communications plan?</p> <p>Tip: build on your matrix of stakeholders, their roles and responsibilities, and add communication messages, mechanisms and timelines</p>
13	Have you undertaken a benchmarking exercise (e.g. current levels of PID adoption) that will enable you to track progress against your strategy?
14	Have you considered how you will monitor and/or measure the success of the strategy?
15	Have you engaged with the international community (e.g. via the Research Data Alliance) to get input into the development of your strategy and to share your progress with others?

Case Study Template - RDA National PID Strategies Working Group

Title	Case Study: [insert country or region to which the national PID approach/strategy applies]
Creator(s)	author(s) of this document including position title, organisation, ORCID(s) and contact details
Date	date this document was created

Features of National PID Approach and/or Strategy

Lead organisation(s)

List the lead organisation(s) and governance structure responsible for developing and/or maintaining the PID approach and/or strategy

Scope

Define the scope of the PID approach and/or strategy (i.e. who it applies to)

Drivers

Describe the drivers behind the PID approach and/or strategy development e.g. wanting to improve accuracy of research information, better track research impact, reduce administrative burden, etc.

Strategy development

Describe the process and timeline through which the PID approach and/or strategy was developed e.g. Advisory Group was formed led by a government agency, there was a consultation period in which xx people and organisations were involved, the process by which agreement was achieved etc. Another e.g. ORCID OR DOI Consortium formed.

Key features

Describe the key features of the PID approach and/or strategy

Key infrastructure

List and describe the key infrastructure (platforms, systems, services) that will activate this national PID approach and/or strategy

Name of infrastructure	Key purpose	List of integrated PIDs
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PIDs

List which functions and PIDs are identified in the strategy e.g. identification of research grants is a function and the PID recommended in the PID approach and/or strategy is CrossRef DOI

Function	PID type	Recommended or required?

Impact and monitoring

Summarise any work to describe or track impact of the approach/strategy, including review and/or monitoring processes

Links

Include any links to relevant documents

Additional

Include any other relevant information

Case Study Template - RDA National PID Strategies Working Group

Title	Case Study: Australia
Creator(s)	<p>Natasha Simons Director, National Coordination Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0635-1998 natasha.simons@ardc.edu.au</p> <p>Linda O'Brien Project Lead, National PID Strategy (Consultant for ARDC) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1477-8652</p> <p>Matthias Liffers Research Data Specialist (Informatics), ARDC https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3639-2080</p>
Date	1 May 2023 (v2)

Features of National PID Approach and/or Strategy

Lead organisation(s)

Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC). A National PID Strategy Taskforce has been established by the ARDC made up of senior stakeholders from the research and government sectors.

Scope

Define the scope of the PID approach and/or strategy (i.e. who it applies to)

The Australian National PID Strategy applies to the entire Australian research and innovation sector. Stakeholders include individuals and organisations in research, government and industry.

Drivers

Describe the drivers behind the PID approach and/or strategy development e.g. wanting to improve accuracy of research information, better track research impact, reduce administrative burden, etc.

The [2021 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap](#) found that *Exponential growth in data across all disciplines will be a critical challenge for NRI over coming years, highlighting the need*

for integration of computing and data infrastructure and the maintenance of a strong digital infrastructure ecosystem. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are a core component of a world class, global digital information ecosystem as they provide a universal, machine-readable method to uniquely identify and connect entities within the ecosystem.

Principle 1 within the NRI is that the *NRI maximises the capability of the research and innovation system to contribute to economic outcomes, national security, social wellbeing and environmental sustainability.* PIDs directly contribute to this by facilitating the development of a connected national information ecosystem across research, government, industry and community.

More specifically for research, PIDs can directly contribute to:

- Improving research efficiency, productivity and reduction in administrative burden
- Improving research reproducibility, provenance and attribution and hence research integrity
- Determining the value of, and return of investment in, research investments
- Understanding the relationship between the elements within the national research and innovation ecosystem with a view to optimising the system
- Tracking research engagement, translation and impact.

Each of the above points create national value, whether through increasing the quality and impact of the research ecosystem or improving efficiency. The September 2022 report commissioned by the ARDC and Australian Access Federation (AAF) called, [Incentives to invest in identifiers: a cost-benefit analysis of persistent identifiers in Australian research systems](#), found potential savings to the Australian research system of \$24 million and 38, 000 person days per year through use of persistent identifiers (PIDs). If these savings are re-applied back into research and development this would result in \$84 million annual economy-wide benefits for Australia ([CSIRO Working Paper](#)).

To realise these anticipated benefits will require a coordinated, comprehensive and collaborative approach to PIDs, bringing together the key stakeholders across the national research, innovation and impact ecosystem. Capturing the potential \$84 million of value will require a national conversation, culminating in a National PID Strategy and Roadmap by November 2023.

Strategy development

Describe the process and timeline through which the PID approach and/or strategy was developed e.g. Advisory Group was formed led by a government agency, there was a consultation period in which xx people and organisations were involved, the process by which agreement was achieved etc. Another e.g. ORCID OR DOI Consortium formed.

The ARDC operates national-scale PID services and these, combined with the Australian ORCID Consortium led by the Australian Access Federation, form a key part of the national research infrastructure. The 2022 PID cost-benefit report highlighted the need for a national

approach in order to maximise the benefits of PID investment in addressing common challenges. In collaboration with AAF, the ARDC's approach is therefore to convene a broad and open national discussion that will result in a widely understood national PID strategy and an accompanying roadmap.

The Strategy and Roadmap are not binding top-down policies. They are rather a stakeholder-driven vision of a future research system optimised through use of PIDs. They seek to provide a shared framework to inform co-investment and policy development by relevant organisations.

In February 2023, a National PID Strategy Taskforce was formed by ARDC chaired by Professor Keith Nugent, DVC-R at the Australian National University (ANU) and includes senior stakeholders from across the sector including the CEO of the Australian Research Council. The purpose of the Taskforce is to:

1. Provide strategic advice to the ARDC on the development of the National PID Strategy and a five year Roadmap
2. Advocate for the engagement and commitment of key stakeholders to the development and implementation of the Strategy and Roadmap
3. Provide advice on a suitable governance structure to oversee the implementation of the Strategy and Roadmap

Also in February 2023, ARDC held an all-day workshop open to anyone who wanted to attend to kick off the national strategy. The workshop initiated a vision for the strategy and resulted in an open call for working group topics and members to explore aspects of the national strategy and feed into the work of the Taskforce in overseeing strategy development.

An update on the Australian National PID Strategy from 4 May 2023 can be found on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7897961>

Key features

Describe the key features of the PID approach and/or strategy

National PID Strategy components and timeline

- Kick-off workshop & call for Working Group topics & members (Feb 2023)
- Taskforce established (Feb 2023)
- Working Groups kick off (May 23) and conclude (June 2023)
- Individual, group and working group submissions open (May 2023)
- Taskforce release draft strategy & roadmap (June 2023) at second workshop Canberra/online
- [TBC July to November 2023]
 - Iterative strategy and roadmap development: release – gather feedback – adjust – release
 - Outreach and communications strategy
 - Final strategy and roadmap release (Nov 2023)

- Roadmap commences (January 2024)

Key infrastructure

List and describe the key infrastructure (platforms, systems, services) that will activate this national PID approach and/or strategy

To be decided, however the following lists the potential infrastructure:

Name of infrastructure	Key purpose	List of integrated PIDs
ARDC Identifier Services ARDC DataCite DOI Consortium Global RAiD Registration Authority	ARDC provides a range of services for research organisations to create and manage persistent identifiers (PIDs).	DOI, RAiD, Handle, IGSN, ROR, ISNI, ORCID and more
AAF Australian ORCID Consortium	Australia's ORCID Consortium led by the Australian Access Federation	ORCID
ARDC Data Discovery portals including Research Data Australia , Research Vocabularies Australia , Research Link Australia , Research Grants Australia	Discovery of research data and related materials	DOI, RAiD, Handle, IGSN, ROR, ISNI, ORCID and more
ARC & NHMRC Grant opportunities portal	Research grant applications	ORCID
Institutional and discipline repositories	Storing, describing, sharing research outputs	Various
Government data repositories and portals (various)	Storing, describing, sharing government data	Various

PIDs

List which functions and PIDs are identified in the strategy e.g. identification of research grants is a function and the PID recommended in the PID approach and/or strategy is CrossRef DOI

The functions and PIDs are yet to be decided. Working Groups have been formed according to the needs of the Strategy and Roadmap and will feed into the work of the National PID Taskforce. Each Working Group will make a submission to the National PID Strategy using the template provided by the National PID Taskforce. Working Group focus areas have been confirmed following an open call for Working Group topics and participation:

1. Engaging Government
2. Grant Identifiers

3. HERDC
4. Instrument Identifiers
5. Non-Traditional Research Output (NTRO) Identifiers
6. Observation Identifiers
7. Organisation and Facility Identifiers
8. Project Identifiers

Additional Working Groups may be needed and formed as the conversation progresses.

A 'general submission' template is also available for anyone (individual, organisation, group) who wishes to submit a use case to the National PID Strategy outside of the Working Groups.

The following table reflects the current state of national PID infrastructure, not necessarily those that will be recommended in the final Strategy and Roadmap (since that conversation is still underway):

Function	PID type	Recommended or required?
Research grants	PURL or DOI	TBC
Research outputs - articles, data, software, instruments, samples and related materials	DOI	
Researchers, contributors	ORCID	
Research projects	RAiD	
Research instruments	DOI, Handle	
Samples and specimens	IGSN, DOI	
Research organisations	ROR	

Impact and monitoring

Summarise any work to describe or track impact of the approach/strategy, including review and/or monitoring processes

Yet to be determined for the National PIS Strategy and Roadmap. Likely to leverage the following:

- ARDC internally tracks and monitors the usage of our PID services. Our co-investment projects are required to provide [impact reporting](#) and PIDs play a major role in this.
- AAF reports usage of the ORCID service to the Australian ORCID Governance and Advisory Groups as well as to the AAF Board.

Links

Include any links to relevant documents

- ARDC National PID Strategy and Roadmap homepage - <https://ardc.edu.au/project/australian-national-persistent-identifier-pid-strategy-and-roadmap/>
- Update: Australian National PID Strategy (4 May 2023) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7897961>
- ARDC PIDs Policy - https://ardc.edu.au/about_us/policies-and-guidelines/persistent-identifiers-policy/

Case Study Template - RDA National PID Strategies Working Group

Title:	National PID Strategy for Canada
Creators:	John Aspler, Manager, Canadian PID Community, Canadian Research Knowledge Network (CRKN), https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7055-4357 , jaspler@crkn.ca Mark Leggott, Chair (Canadian PID Advisory Committee), Director of International Relations, Digital Research Alliance of Canada Team: Mark Goodwin, James MacGregor, Rebecca Ross, Lee Wilson, Claire Duncan, and the CPIDAC
Date:	May 20, 2022; Updated May 10, 2023

Features of National PID Approach and/or Strategy

Lead organisation(s)

1. Canadian Research Knowledge Network (CRKN)
2. Canadian PID Advisory Committee (CPIDAC)
 1. ORCID-CA Governing Committee (OCGC)
 2. DataCite Canada Governing Committee (DCCGC)
3. Digital Research Alliance of Canada (The Alliance)

Scope

The development of a Canadian National PID Strategy is in its early stages and is intended to promote best practices and ensure that any researcher or research organization in Canada can make use of PIDs, ideally at an appropriate and equitable fee scale.

In 2021, CRKN, on behalf of the CPIDAC and in partnership with the Alliance, [hired a consultant \(MoreBrains\)](#) to develop a “roadmap to a roadmap” to help the Canadian PID community identify the pre-conditions for success; necessary actions, initiatives, and stakeholders to ensure successful development and implementation of an eventual PID Strategy for Canada.

In 2022, MoreBrains finalized the roadmap and continued to support the next phase of strategy development, which will include a living list of challenges, recommendations on how PIDs can solve these challenges, accessible primers as well as slides on PIDs and their value proposition for communication, models for PID-optimized workflows, and evidence of return on investment.

Drivers

Reducing administrative burden, reducing cost, making research more FAIR and Open, developing the digital research infrastructure of the future, impact tracking, and more.

Strategy development

In 2020, CRKN took over administration of the DataCite Canada Consortium (DCAN) from the National Research Council of Canada jointly with the Alliance. Consequently, CRKN had begun to provide support for two PID consortia: DCAN and ORCID-CA. When considering governance models for DCAN, staff looked to the existing ORCID-CA governance structure, which included the OCGC, comprised of members, and the ORCID-CA Advisory Committee (OCAC) comprised of non-member stakeholder organizations (e.g., academic library consortia, digital infrastructure, provincial/national funders). However, instead of creating separate advisory committees, the OCAC expanded in scope and function to include both PID consortia, becoming the CPIDAC.

The CPIDAC's scope grew to include both advising the two existing PID consortia and thinking beyond just ORCID-CA and DCAN - looking to a broader PID strategy for Canada. At this time, participation in the committee grew to include double the representatives (see committee members and organizations here: <https://www.crkn-rcdr.ca/en/orcid-ca-governance>).

In 2021, CRKN was successful in securing funding from the Alliance for a first phase of a PID consultation. The CPIDAC then developed a [request for proposals](#) by forming a working group made up of CRKN and Alliance staff and several members of the committee. CRKN issued the RFP in September 2021 and the CPIDAC working group evaluated the proposals and made a recommendation to CRKN. MoreBrains Cooperative was hired in November 2021 to deliver a product in early 2022. The original RFP was deemed too ambitious in scope for the proposed timeline and budget, which led to the proposal that MoreBrains help develop a "Roadmap to a Roadmap" ahead of a second phase of consulting and work being done in Canada.

In 2022, in a report titled "[Towards a national PID strategy for Canada - Vers une stratégie nationale sur les PID pour le Canada](#)," MoreBrains outlined an approach and identified gaps to fill before a complete strategy could be developed. Participants included university leadership, researchers, professional associations, federal and provincial funders, technical experts, and more. In this phase, MoreBrains conducted a landscape analysis, six one-on-one interviews, and three 12-15 person workshops. The workshops were designed and divided according to three themes: 1) Strategy; 2) Implementation; and 3) Challenges and Opportunities.

We [announced these findings](#), which included a set of recommendations based on community consultation, many of which are already underway, confirming our overall approach is aligned with international partners and other jurisdictions. They identified challenges and priorities for the future, including building trust and enhancing communication between stakeholders, improving and connecting fragmented infrastructure across Canadian institutions, highlighting the urgency to the broader community, and telling a compelling story about the value of PIDs.

A community of dedicated Canadian PID experts and enthusiasts already exists, so the most important elements of these recommendations are to expand that community, identify a set of priority use cases for PIDs in Canada, and show how PIDs can resolve Canadian research challenges while leveraging opportunities for research nationally. Developing a strategy for PID adoption and implementation is a journey. In the report, MoreBrains identified the starting point, mapped the gaps in coverage or awareness of PIDs and the critical areas where, for example,

PIDs could help to improve research effectiveness or simplify bureaucracy, and identified stakeholders who must be consulted and interventions for the next steps of the journey.

Expected outputs of the next phase of consultation, which will be published in part in 2023, will include blog posts, PID primers, slides, and briefings for targeted audiences, and a report around research challenges in Canada and which PIDs can resolve which challenges. Two largescale workshops of 20-25 participants have already been held on the topics of 1) Infrastructure interoperability between funders and institutions; and 2) Institutional integrations and uptake. Over 40 stakeholders participated across both workshops from across many academic sectors - funders, government, universities, research offices, infrastructure, etc.

Based on these workshops, a pitch to government is being developed to seek additional resources and to help explain the urgency and importance of PIDs. The CPIDAC will meet in June 2023 to receive the results of these two workshops and this phase's project outputs. Additional work is anticipated on a new phase beginning Q3 2023.

This work has been presented to the RDA National PID Strategy WG, and was also presented in person at the RDA conference in early 2023 (including at the DataCite Connect event).

Key features

It will include a living list of challenges, recommendations on how PIDs can solve these challenges, accessible primers as well as slides on PIDs and their value proposition for communication, models for PID-optimized workflows, and evidence of return on investment.

Key infrastructure

The Strategy is not sufficiently developed to identify which infrastructure should be prioritized - identifying this infrastructure is a key priority. However, based on some of the work we are already doing at CRKN, the Alliance, and through the CPIDAC, we can identify some areas of success (e.g., [the ORCID-OJS integration](#)) and commonly used systems in Canada.

Name of infrastructure	Key purpose	List of integrated PIDs
OJS	Open Publishing Platform	ORCID, DOI
DSpace	Digital Repository	DOI, ORCID (soon)

PIDs

The Strategy is not sufficiently developed to identify which PIDs will be recommended for particular functions, nor is it certain in what capacities various PIDs can be required of different stakeholders (e.g., the Federal Government of Canada is not likely to mandate ORCID, even as it will hopefully include a connection to ORCID as an option). However, based on existing Canadian infrastructure and PID consortia, we can certainly speak to some likely candidates.

Function	PID type	Recommended or required?
Existing consortia support	ORCID	
Existing consortia support	DataCite DOI	

Considering use case for centralized support	Crossref DOI	
Considering use case for centralized support	ROR	

Impact and monitoring

Not possible at this stage.

Links

2022, [Developing a Canadian PID Strategy: Results and Next Steps](#)

2022, [Towards a national PID strategy for Canada - Vers une stratégie nationale sur les PID pour le Canada](#)

2022, [MoreBrains and CRKN presentation at NDSF 2022](#)

2022, [Persistent Identifiers: Current Landscape and Future Trends](#)

2021, [Request for Proposal for a PID Consultant](#)

2021, [Canadian PID Webinar Series](#)

2020, [Persistent Identifiers in Canada: ORCID-CA and DataCite Canada - White Paper](#)

2020, [Persistent Identifiers in Canada – Position Paper](#)

[PID Governance](#) in Canada

- [CPIDAC Terms of Reference](#)
- [DataCite Canada Governing Committee Terms of Reference](#)
- [ORCID-CA Governing Committee Terms of Reference](#)

Case Study Template - RDA National PID Strategies Working Group

Title	Case Study: Czech Republic
Creator(s)	Hana Heringová, Head of the National Centre for Persistent Identifiers, National Library of Technology, https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2962-3936 , e-mail: hana.heringova@techlib.cz , Petra Černohlávková, Head of the Centre for Repositories and Metadata Management, National Library of Technology, https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8683-6156 , e-mail: petra.cernohlavkova@techlib.cz
Date	April 30, 2023

Features of National PID Approach and/or Strategy

Lead organisation(s)

List the lead organisation(s) and governance structure responsible for developing and/or maintaining the PID approach and/or strategy

The Czech National PID strategy is driven by the National Library of Technology in Prague (NTK). NTK is the largest and the oldest library of science and technology literature in the Czech Republic. Since 1991 has been operating under the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic. According to its statute, NTK performs the function of a publicly accessible scientific and technical library, which is part of the Czech information infrastructure for R&D. It provides access to information and its reuse at the national level and in the public interest, especially through information services and the information infrastructure operated to support R&D&I, and education.

At the national level, NTK provides a supporting platform for research performing organisations and manages the National Licensing Centre for Electronic Information Resources (CzechELib), currently serving 125 members (Czech research institutions). Beside others, NTK also has been supporting the National Repository of Grey Literature, the Czech National ISSN Centre, which assigns ISSN numbers and registers serial publications in the Czech Republic and a workplace for The Digital Library for Grey Literature.

From this perspective, NTK can offer a coordinated national approach and central support for integration and adoption of ORCID and DataCide in the Czech Republic. First of all, in 2019, the Czech Government approved the [Action plan for National Strategy of Open Access to Scientific](#)

[Information for 2017-2020](#) (in Czech only). One of its measures was to introduce unique identifiers for authors (ORCID) as a mandatory part of the Czech National CRIS – [IS VaVal](#) 2.0). This national R&D&I Information System collects information on R&D&I supported from the public budget in the Czech Republic and is the only authorised, complete, and binding source of this information.

Later in 2020, the [R&D&I Council](#), which administers and operates the National CRIS – [IS VaVal](#), released a [call for research organizations to introduce ORCID](#) and request iDs to be connected to publications reported on the national CRIS in order to improve research evaluation and bibliometric analysis. Nevertheless, for unresolved concerns related to GDPR, ORCID has never been made mandatory in IS VaVal, only recommended.

In 2020, the Czech Government approved funding for NTK to lead a 7 years project "National Centre for Information Support of R&D&I" (2021-2027) to increase the quality and efficiency of the national R&D&I environment and to reduce administrative burden on the staff of RPOs. One of the activities was establishing and leading a national ORCID consortium to support implementation of European standards into the national landscape.

In 2021, NTK and ORCID took the steps toward the establishment of a formal community of practice by co-hosting a virtual workshop "ORCID in the Czech Republic: towards National Consortium."

Analysis of needs for persistent author identifiers (ORCID iD) among the research institutions in 2021/2022 <https://doi.org/10.48813/6erb-z009> provided following recommendations:

- Seek a decision at government level on the mandatory use of ORCID iDs already in grant applications and especially in reporting research results to the National CRIS - IS VaVal.
- Build up a centralised support for the ORCID and provide financial resources to institutions in the initial phase.
- Support integration of ORCID into the information/submission systems of funders in order to automatically assign successful projects into the ORCID profile.

Due to the lack of financial resources to support the research institutions to join the national consortium and integration of ORCID, this project activities was transferred to the following EU funded project CARDS.

In Dec 2021, thanks to the EU project DICE - Data Infrastructure Capacity for EOSC, NTK became part of the international DataCite Consortium EUDAT and since that could assign persistent DOIs free of charge until mid-2023. The assumption was that NTK will subsequently establish and lead the Czech consortium for DataCite.

In 2023, NTK has received EU funding¹ for 2023-2028 to establish a unified environment for sharing and effective management of information resources and to participate in the creation of a common framework for the implementation of data-oriented components of the Open Science in the Czech Republic, especially within the Open/FAIR Data and EOSC pillars. As part of this effort, NTK set up the National PID Centre – a specialized team supporting PIDs implementation on a national level. NTK will act as a leader of the national ORCID and DataCite consortia that will be operating under the PID Centre starting June 1st 2023.

¹ Project CARDS (Czech Academic Research and Discovery Services), Registration Number CZ.02.01.01/00/22_004/0004342, more information available [here](#) and [here](#)

Currently, NTK is negotiating its role, as a coordinator of the Czech National Open Science Strategy, with the Czech Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports, R&D&I Council², to involve other major stakeholders within the Czech R&D environment – e.g. research funding and performing organisations (Czech Academy of Sciences, public universities etc.), EOSC.cz and other actors. Once this structure is set up and operating, the work on the national PID strategy should be embedded into its activities.

Scope

Define the scope of the the PID approach and/or strategy (i.e. who it applies to)

The PID strategy will primarily apply to:

TARGET INSTITUTIONS:

- Public research performing organisations (RPOs): Higher Education Institutions and Research organizations
- Research funding organizations (RFOs): Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports, Czech Science Foundation, Technology Agency of the Czech Republic etc.
- Policymakers: Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports; Research, Development and Innovation Council (R&D&I Council)
- Libraries: National library, National Library of Technology, academic libraries
- Publishers based in Czechia
- Service providers, research infrastructures

TARGET GROUPS:

- Researchers
- Librarians
- Open Science/Open Access managers/coordinators
- CRIS system managers
- Repository managers
- Other research support positions, e.g. data stewards, data curators

Drivers

Describe the drivers behind the PID approach and/or strategy development e.g. wanting to improve accuracy of research information, better track research impact, reduce administrative burden, etc.

The main driver is ensuring that the Czech R&D environment can benefit from effective implementation of PIDs on a large scale. This goal should be supported by the first phase of the planned cost-benefit analysis that should quantify the potential of financial savings due to the

² The Czech Research, Development and Innovation Council is an advisory body to the Czech government operated by the Office of the Government, more information available [here](#)

PIDs implementation. This potential is already being acknowledged and demanded by Czech researchers and the R&D community.

The national PID strategy is ultimately supposed to ensure a formal framework for management and access to PIDs and introduce them as a standard into the Czech R&D environment.

Strategy development

Describe the process and timeline through which the PID approach and/or strategy was developed e.g. Advisory Group was formed led by a government agency, there was a consultation period in which xx people and organisations were involved, the process by which agreement was achieved etc. Another e.g. ORCID OR DOI Consortium formed.

We are in very early stages of the development of the formal national PID strategy, however some concrete measures and decisions for adoption of PIDs have already been taken - NTK has been granted funding to create the National PID Centre as well as two national consortia (ORCID and DataCite) and cover all the related fees for its members between 2023 and 2028. The National PID Centre and its surrounding community made up mostly of ORCID and DataCite national consortia members and EOSC-CZ Metadata working group should be the key contributors to the creation of the Czech PID strategy.

We expect that building a solid national PID strategy will be a long-term process underpinned by experience with running the national consortia and the planned cost-benefit analysis. We would like to see some first concrete strategy draft in about 3 years from now. As mentioned above, we plan on formulating the strategy as part of the more holistic approach towards National Open Science strategy for the Czech Republic, which will be under development

Key features

Describe the key features of the PID approach and/or strategy

The features of the strategy will be guided by its ultimate goal which is to guarantee centralized support on the national level via continued funding of the National PID Centre and its services (including continued support and further development of national ORCID and DataCite consortia) that would enable further development of currently supported PIDs and support of new ones. From the perspective of the National PID Centre, we observe the need for a functional process for selecting new relevant PIDs and defining their priority that should be driven on the national level and the Czech research community's needs. Other features will be determined later.

Key infrastructure

List and describe the key infrastructure (platforms, systems, services) that will activate this national PID approach and/or strategy

Name of infrastructure	Key purpose	List of integrated PIDs
e-infra	This large infrastructure will build the National Repository Platform in the upcoming years. That should greatly facilitate adoption of PIDs.	TBD
National CRIS - IS VaVal (R&D Information System)	National research information system. We plan on working with Research, Development and Innovation Council (in charge of IS VaVal) on integrating global PIDs into their submission processes as required. Nowadays it uses mostly local identifiers.	TBD
Institutional CRIS systems	Various institutional CRIS systems at Czech RPOs. OBD (Personal Bibliographic Database) application is an outstanding case of an institutional CRIS system in the Czech Republic developed locally by a Czech company DERS. An ORCID integration for OBD is currently in development.	TBD, OBD ORCID in process
Institutional or subject repositories	There are several repositories in the Czech republic collecting different objects, some are already using PIDs but there is still enough room to improve and really integrate those PIDs, not only allow their evidence.	Handle, DOI, maybe other
Major research funders	Grant application processes	TBD
Local publishers	Content submission processes	TBD

PIDs

List which functions and PIDs are identified in the strategy e.g. identification of research grants is a function and the PID recommended in the PID approach and/or strategy is CrossRef DOI

Function	PID type	Recommended or required?
Identification of researchers	ORCID	Recommended
Identification of research outputs	DOI (DataCite, CrossRef)	Recommended
Identification of organizations	ROR	Recommended
Identification of books	ISBN	Recommended
Identification of serial publications	ISSN	Recommended

Identification of printed music	ISMN	Recommended
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We will likely look into support for additional PIDs such as IGSN (through DataCite), RaiD and others.

Impact and monitoring

Summarise any work to describe or track impact of the approach/strategy, including review and/or monitoring processes

NTK will deliver a cost-benefit analysis in two phases - in 2024 and 2028 (funded by project CARDS). The first phase will capture the current status of the selected PIDs usage within the Czech R&D environment and potential financial benefits of their effective implementation. The second phase will capture the progress in use of PIDs from 2024.

We will also set up regular monitoring of progress regarding adoption of ORCID, DOI (and other priority PIDs) with a set of identified key metrics as part of the National PID Centre impact assessment.

There is also a monitoring mechanism embedded in the CARDS project.

Links

Include any links to relevant documents

- [National R&D&I Policy of the Czech Republic 2021+](#)
- [CARDS project](#)
- General recommendations for metadata description of research outputs and research data - used at RFOs includes PIDs (in Czech only), <https://doi.org/10.48813/yt6w-6h15>
- Towards a national ORCID consortium in the Czech Republic, 2021, <https://info.orcid.org/towards-a-national-orcid-consortium-in-the-czech-republic/>
- Analysis of the effectiveness of and interest in centralised provision of the ORCID id persistent identifier, 2022 (in Czech only) <https://doi.org/10.48813/6erb-z009>

Additional

Include any other relevant information

As the Czech national PID strategy is in very early stages of development, all that has been stated above is to a high degree preliminary and subject to change.

Case Study Template - RDA National PID Strategies Working Group

Title	Case Study: Finland
Creator(s)	Jessica Parland-von Essen Development Manager CSC https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4460-3906
Date	2022-06-10

Features of National PID Approach and/or Strategy

Lead organisation(s)

Representatives from the following PID service providers have participated in the on-going work, among many other PID managers and stakeholders:

CSC – IT Center for Science

- DataCite Finland Consortium lead
- ORCID Consortium Coordinator
- ePIC Consortium member

National Library of Finland

- URN service provider
- Finnish ISBN, ISNI and ISSN Agencies

National Land Survey

- Geodata identifiers

Digital and Population Data Services Agency

- Government interoperability service provider

Natural History Museum/University of Helsinki

- GBIF partner

Scope

The roadmap is focused on researcher's needs, but aims at a wide definition of research data, encompassing as much of government open data as possible.

Drivers

The main driver has been the need of coordination and information sharing among PID service providers, managers and owners. As new types of PIDs and services emerge, there is a need for collaboration to support good management practices and implementation of PIDs. Issues with scientific reproducibility as well as the development of the national research information hub research.fi have spawned interest in describing a shared target state. Finland also has a strong tradition of building national services to support interoperability with services like finto.fi and the national interoperability workbench, <https://suomidigi.fi/ohjeet-ja-tuki/yhteentoimivuusalusta>.

Strategy development

The URN has been a strong PID system in Finland since its first definition in 1994. The Finnish National Library has offered PID services and promoted the use of PIDs since. As the landscape diversified, an informal network was started some ten years ago. The PID Forum Finland wiki (<https://wiki.eduuni.fi/display/CscPidVerkosto/PID-verkosto>) was created in 2016 and the network has usually met twice a year to share updates and information. In 2018 the network produced a report on persistent identifiers for the Ministry of Finance, that is responsible for public data management. In 2016 the ORCID consortium was founded. The DataCite Finland Consortium was founded in 2021. Both these consortia are facilitated and supported by CSC. Currently CSC is also developing and maintaining the Research Information Hub mentioned above and looking at implementing RAiD. All this work is funded by the Ministry of Education. CSC is also taking part in the FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT Horizon projects, both of which are taking PID development forward within the EOSC.

The work on the PID roadmap began in 2021 and has progressed slowly but steadily. The informal character of the network producing it creates some issues with the mandate. On the other hand there is documented interest from the government in this work and within open science there is a culture of working this way, thanks to the Open Science and Research Coordination work, where much policy work is done. (<https://www.avointiede.fi/en>)

Key features

The PID roadmap is focused on building a shared understanding of the target state for the PID landscape in Finland and supporting open linked data implementation and interoperability. The target state has been formulated with the following value proposition:

Traceable and unambiguous information (about digital) objects can be found through different channels and can be linked to in a reliable way now and in the future.

Our aim is to ensure data quality and sustainable use of persistent identifiers. The roadmap has the following contents (WiP):

1. Different traits, contexts and requirements and the advantages of managed use of identifiers
2. How to implement and manage national PID policies
 - a. Raising awareness and competence
 - b. Building trust
 - c. Organising the infrastructures

Key infrastructure

Name of infrastructure	Key purpose	List of integrated PIDs
Fairdata.fi	Research data publication, metadata hub and preservation service	DOI, URN, ORCID (upda
Research.fi	National research data hub.	Current draft: ADSbibcode - Astrophysics Data System - Bibliographic Reference Code (en) ARK - Archival Resource Key (en) arXiv - arXiv identifier scheme (en) BusinessID - Y-tunnus (fi) (en) Crossref_funders - Crossref Funder Registry (en) DOI - Digital Object Identifier (en)

		<p>EAN13 - The 13-digit International Article Number (en)</p> <p>GRID - Global Research Identifier Database (en)</p> <p>Handle - Handle (en)</p> <p>ISBN - International Standard Book Number (en)</p> <p>eISBN - electronic International Standard Book Number (en)</p> <p>ISNI - International Standard Name Identifier (en)</p> <p>ISSN - International Standard Serial Number (en)</p> <p>eISSN - electronic International Standard Serial Number (en)</p> <p>ISTC - The International Standard Text Code (en)</p> <p>LSID - Life Sciences Identifier (en)</p> <p>Orcid - Open Researcher and Contributor ID (en)</p> <p>PIC - (EC) partner identity code (en)</p> <p>PMID - PubMed ID (en)</p> <p>PURL - persistent uniform resource locator (en)</p> <p>QID - Wikidata identifier (en)</p> <p>RAID - Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) (en)</p> <p>ROR - Research Organization Registry (en)</p> <p>ScopusAuthorID - Scopus Author ID (en)</p> <p>UPC - Universal Product Code (en)</p> <p>URI - Uniform Resource Identifier (en)</p> <p>URL - Uniform Resource Locator (en)</p> <p>URN - Uniform Resource Name (en)</p> <p>VAT-number - VAT number (en)</p>
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		Virta-id - Virta-id (en) JuFo-id - Publication Forum publication channel ID (en) SF-edu-ID - Tilastokeskuksen oppilaitostunnus
National Library	Semantic artefacts, publications	URN (ISBN, ISNI, ISSN)
National interoperability services (?)	Semantic artefacts	URN?

PIDs

Function	PID type	Comment
Researchers, persons	ORCID; ISNI	ORCID cannot be created posthumously
Organisations	VAT-number (not resolvable yet) RoR ISNI PIC (not resolvable yet) SF-edu-ID (not resolvable yet)	
Funding decisions	URN	Hosted by research.fi
Publications	CrossRef DOI, URN JuFo-id - Publication Forum publication channel ID (en) ISSN ISBN PMID	URN used with ISBN and for instance for file level identification under CrossRef DOI
Datasets	DataCite DOI, URN	DataCite DOI is given strictly to data that can be cited in a precise way
Specimens	doi	underway
Infrastructures	URN	Hosted by research.fi

Concepts, data types	PURL, URN, URI, QID	Hosted by dvv, research.fi, National library, Wikidata
Research Activity	RAiD	underway

Impact and monitoring

This has not yet been defined.

Links

<https://wiki.eduuni.fi/display/CscPidVerkosto/PID-verkosto>

<https://research.fi>

Additional information

CSC is also currently working on a PID architecture that describes the landscape including the internal PID Microservice for identifier management.

Case Study Template - RDA National PID Strategies Working Group

Title	Case Study: Germany
Creator(s)	<p>Antonia C. Schrader, Open Science Officer at Helmholtz Open Science Office, Helmholtz Association, https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7080-634X antonia.schrader@os.helmholtz.de [corresponding author]</p> <p>Stephanie Glagla-Dietz, staff of GND service sciences at German National Library, https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8762-3005</p> <p>Andreas Czerniak, staff of Bielefeld University Library, https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3883-4169</p> <p>Lena Messerschmidt, Open Science Officer at Helmholtz Open Science Office, Helmholtz Association, https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3406-9933</p> <p>Paul Vierkant, Outreach manager at DataCite, https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4448-3844</p> <p>Frauke Ziedorn, project manager at Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB) – German National Library of Science and Technology, https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1143-781X</p>
Date	April 28, 2023

Features of National PID Approach and/or Strategy

Lead organisation(s)

List the lead organisation(s) and governance structure responsible for developing and/or maintaining the PID approach and/or strategy

DataCite,
the German National Library (DNB),

the Helmholtz Open Science Office, Helmholtz Association,
the German National Library of Science and Technology (TIB)
the Bielefeld University Library

Scope

Define the scope of the the PID approach and/or strategy (i.e. who it applies to)

The creation and publication of a national PID roadmap for Germany will be a main outcome of the project "PID Network Germany – Network for fostering persistent identifiers in science and culture" that is funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) and scheduled to run for 36 months. The project officially started on March 01, 2023 and aims to establish a network of already existing and currently forming actors around the persistent identification of persons, organizations, publications, resources, and infrastructures in the field of digital communication in science and culture in Germany. PID Network Germany pursues an overarching approach across the boundaries of individual scientific institutions and research disciplines. The project description provides further insight into the objectives of the project: <https://doi.org/10.48440/os.helmholtz.059> (only in German).

The scope of the roadmap is to present a perspective for a networked PID landscape in Germany. The focus is on a strategic approach to the topic in a cooperatively operating information infrastructure that on the one hand provides individual institutions with a framework for local PID applications and on the other hand the systemic advantages of a widespread and consistent implementation of PID systems in Germany.

Drivers

Describe the drivers behind the PID approach and/or strategy development e.g. wanting to improve accuracy of research information, better track research impact, reduce administrative burden, etc.

In Germany, the need to use Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for the permanently reliable identification of the resources associated with research processes, the actors involved, and their research products is recognized as a fundamental principle both on a national and on a local level, for example in academic organizations.

However, this is also accompanied by new requirements for the efficient usage of PIDs in the research process and their dissemination. At the same time, users are confronted with a large variety of very different offerings with different focal points serving different needs. In addition to international approaches, such as DataCite and Crossref, there are more nationally oriented systems, such as the German National Library's "urn:nbn:de" namespace using the Uniform Resource Name (URN). Beyond this, a broad landscape of specific and locally oriented PID systems contributes to the PID landscape. These are often geared to the needs of the specific domain and implemented via the Handle system and the associated Handle.Net Registry (HNR). Initiatives such as the PIDForum (pidforum.org), help with internationally significant

issues, but a void remains at the national level. A coordinated networking and promotion of PID systems in Germany is a desideratum. This includes the need to support the application of PIDs. However, in order to exploit the full benefits in science and culture, the exchange between and thus the interoperability of PID systems in Germany must also be promoted.

Strategy development

Describe the process and timeline through which the PID approach and/or strategy was developed e.g. Advisory Group was formed led by a government agency, there was a consultation period in which xx people and organisations were involved, the process by which agreement was achieved etc. Another e.g. ORCID OR DOI Consortium formed.

The publication of the national PID roadmap for Germany is planned for the end of the project, which means by the beginning of the year 2026.

In a first step, all findings of the project will be consolidated and expanded by impulses from international efforts and developments. Based on this a draft of the PID roadmap for Germany will be prepared by the project partners.

In a next step, the draft of the PID Roadmap will be revised during a public comment period. This will ensure the visibility of the document and foster participation of a broad audience. In this way, further suggestions for the PID roadmap can be obtained and incorporated, thereby increasing the acceptance of the roadmap.

The PID Roadmap for Germany will be published as a stand-alone Open Access publication in digital and printed form.

Key features

Describe the key features of the PID approach and/or strategy

In the course of the project, the organization of workshops and webinars with a focus on 10 different PID use cases (see section "PIDs"), the conduct of a quantitative and qualitative survey on the PID's landscape in Germany and the creation of use cases and guidelines for the optimization of PID metadata in identifier and aggregation systems are planned. All those findings will result in recommendations and suggestions for the further development of PID systems in the national PID roadmap of Germany. Furthermore, impulses from international efforts, such as the "PID Policy" of the EOSC, the "PID Strategy of Dutch Research Council (NWO)" in the Netherlands, the work of the "Research Identifier National Coordinating Committee (RINCC)" of the "UK PID consortium" in the United Kingdom and of the RDA working group on „National PID Strategies" will be included.

Key infrastructure

List and describe the key infrastructure (platforms, systems, services) that will activate this national PID approach and/or strategy

Name of infrastructure	Key purpose	List of integrated PIDs
German national bibliography	The aim is to offer stable and reliable bridges for the construction of a knowledge graph of culture and science.	Crossref & DataCite DOIs, URN:NBN, ORCID iDs, ROR iDs
Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE)	Since 2004, Bielefeld University Library has been productively developing and operating the scientific search engine BASE with the aim of indexing OA content from publication infrastructures, especially repositories, as comprehensively as possible.	Crossref & DataCite DOIs, URN:NBN, ORCID iDs, ROR iDs
DataCite Consortium & ORCID Germany Consortium	TIB is the lead organisation for both services. This will definitely take into account when creating the PID roadmap for Germany	DOIs, ORCID IDs

PIDs

List which functions and PIDs are identified in the strategy e.g. identification of research grants is a function and the PID recommended in the PID approach and/or strategy is CrossRef DOI

Function	PID type (Examples:)	Recommended or required?
Research data	DataCite DOI, URN	Not yet defined
Instruments	DataCite DOI	Not yet defined
Academic Conferences	DataCite DOI GND (The Integrated Authority File) ID	Not yet defined
The persistent identification of cultural objects, holdings and collections and their contexts (associated events, actors, concepts) in the context of Humanities	GND ID	Not yet defined
Organizations & Projects	ROR GND ID Gepiris Crossref Funder Registry	Not yet defined

	RAiD	
Persons	ORCID GND ID	Not yet defined
Physical Objects	RRID IGSN	Not yet defined
PIDs for open access publication services and research information systems	No standard established at the moment	Not yet defined
Software	No standard established at the moment	Not yet defined
Text publication	Crossref & DataCite DOI URN	Not yet defined

Impact and monitoring

Summarise any work to describe or track impact of the approach/strategy, including review and/or monitoring processes

The progress and impact of the project will be measured and monitored through the collection of quantitative indicators. The different systems of the project partners as well as ORCID Inc. and ROR will be queried. If possible, indicators for all 10 PID use cases should be measured. These include for example the following indicators:

- Number of registered DataCite DOIs by scientific institutions in Germany.
- Number of registered DataCite-DOIs that have a link to further resources via a related-Identifier relationship.
- Number of ROR implementations at scientific institutions in Germany.
- Number of GND records that have an ORCID iD or a ROR ID.
- Etc.

How the impact of the roadmap can be measured and tracked is still up for discussion.

Links

Include any links to relevant documents

Project proposal: <https://doi.org/10.48440/os.helmholtz.059> (only in German)

Project website (will be launched by June 2023): <https://www.pid-network.de>

Additional

Include any other relevant information

Case Study - RDA National PID Strategies KOREA (KISTI)

Title	Case Study: KISTI
Creator(s)	Jayhoon Kim, Data Standardization Team Leader, KISTI +82-42-869-1888, jay.kim@kisti.re.kr
Date	2022-05-21

Features of National PID Approach and/or Strategy

Lead organisation(s)

- KISTI is one of the DOI registration agencies (Korea DOI Center (<https://www.doi.or.kr>))
- KISTI is one of the designated managing institutions of Korean R&D outputs by Korean law (Research papers and articles)

Scope

- KISTI broadly collect, consolidate research articles, patents, research data, trend information, etc. and provide them to Korean academic and research institutes, corporates.
- KISTI DOI RA is one of functionality explained above and focuses on Korean intellectual properties (Research articles, patents, Research data, etc.)
- KISTI examines and improves Korean R&D outputs (metadata and fulltext). Those activities include issuing domestic unique id and author/institution disambiguation.

Drivers

- KISTI wants to curate scientific information including Korean R&D outputs of higher state of identification for better curation, tracking research impact, analysing research outcomes.
- DOI RA is a strategic infrastructure for KISTI to curate research outputs and intellectual properties. KISTI support Korean societies to stimulate better visibilities of their journal articles around the world.

Strategy development

- 2008~current: Designated as Korean R&D outputs managing institution (research papers and articles) by law.

- Early 2010~current: Internal identifier issuing and machine learning based identification on authors and their institutions
- 2016~current: Working as a DOI registration agency from 2016. Expanding persistent identifier collaboration with various RAs (ISNI RAs in Korea, ORCID and DOI)
- 2022: Experimental research project on comprehensive identifier database development. This project aims to develop testbed database of various identifiers (content, author, data, etc.). Target identifiers are elements appeared in KISTI's remit Korean research articles.

Key features

- KISTI's mission is to curate collect, consolidate, and provide scientific information to Korean researchers and institutions. It includes but is not limited to.
 - Curating Korean R&D outputs. Curate them higher state of identification for better curation, tracking research impact, analysing research outcomes.
 - DOI RA management. Issuing DOIs to Korean research outputs, Intellectual properties, research data
 - Support Korean societies to stimulate better visibilities of their journal articles around the world.
 - Collaborate for better curation (identification and interlinking) with domestic and global scientific information management institutions, publishers and identifier managing agencies.

Key infrastructure

List and describe the key infrastructure (platforms, systems, services) that will activate this national PID approach and/or strategy

Name of infrastructure	Key purpose	List of integrated PIDs
Korea DOI Center	Issuing DOIs to Korean research outputs, Intellectual properties, research data	DOI
KISTI's experimental comprehensive identifier testbed (in progress)	Interlinking (literature, author, data) elements with identifiers in Korean scholarly articles.	DOI, ISNI, ORCID, ROAR, WoS and SCOPUS author ID, Korean national author ID

PIDs

List which functions and PIDs are identified in the strategy e.g., identification of research grants is a function and the PID recommended in the PID approach and/or strategy is CrossRef DOI

Function	PID type	Recommended or required?
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Korean R&D outputs management	DOI (literature and data), Korean research funding ID, Korean national research ID	
Issuing DOIs to Korean research outputs, Intellectual properties, research data	DOI, ISNI, ORCID, ROR, WoS and SCOPUS author ID, Korean national author ID	This project is in progress. So, its usefulness, value, sustainability should be evaluated.

Impact and monitoring

- KISTI's curation activities are reported and monitored to Korean ministry of science and technology.
- KISTI plans new research projects every 3 years in all divisions. It affects even essential infrastructure works (e.g., DOI RA management)
 - KISTI's current key concern is to identify accurately literature, authors, institutions, references and interlink them well. In this context, one of DOI RA's role is to track impact of Korean research outputs. (We named it as "Comprehensive interlinking identifiers)

Links

None.

Additional

None.

Fin.

Case Study Template - RDA National PID Strategies Working Group

Title	Case Study: The Netherlands
Creator(s)	author(s) of this document including position title, organisation, ORCID(s) and contact details Gül Akcaova, Project Manager Innovation, https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9060-4518 , Gul.Akcaova@surf.nl
Date	27-05-2022

Features of National PID Approach and/or Strategy

Lead organisation(s)

List the lead organisation(s) and governance structure responsible for developing and/or maintaining the PID approach and/or strategy

- NWO,
- DANS-KNAW,
- UKB,
- SURF,
- CWTS-Leiden University

Scope

Define the scope of the the PID approach and/or strategy (i.e. who it applies to)

Organize alignment and organize adoption in the research information landscape for funders, institutions, researchers, research stewards, service providers and publishers

Drivers

Describe the drivers behind the PID approach and/or strategy development e.g. wanting to improve accuracy of research information, better track research impact, reduce administrative burden, etc.

Two complementary movements have energized the need for improved information about research: Open Science and Responsible Management of Research Information. In this

context, Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) play an important role. PIDs are also an essential part of the FAIR data principles. With the help of PIDs, digital objects can be identified and reused in a more persistent and less ambiguous way.

International adoption of PIDs such as ORCID for researchers and RoR for organisations, coincides with key developments in The Netherlands. A sample of Dutch initiatives that could benefit from coordinated use of PIDs include open access, open data, data management plans, and responsible research assessment, as well as the possibility of a national Open Knowledge Base. PIDs provide additional structure to research information (metadata) while also enabling durable links between research objects, institutions, funding awards, and researchers.

Strategy development

Describe the process and timeline through which the PID approach and/or strategy was developed e.g. Advisory Group was formed led by a government agency, there was a consultation period in which xx people and organisations were involved, the process by which agreement was achieved etc. Another e.g. ORCID OR DOI Consortium formed.

To address the possibility of employing PIDs in a coordinated way, and to find alignment between present and future initiatives, the PID advisory board (NWO, DANS-KNAW, UKB, SURF and CWTS-Leiden University) requested the development of a national PID roadmap. This request led to the installment of a working group with representatives of eScience Center, Utrecht University, Leiden University, 4TU, KB, DANS-KNAW, Saxion and SURF. Their work provides a first step for engaging the broader community on the content and potential of a national PID roadmap. After delivering a document 'towards a national PID roadmap' we held an open consultation and 15 people from various organizations were involved and provided input. With the input the working group will refine the described two use cases and based on the new version actions will be defined with the stakeholders. In the next month's other use cases will be described as well.

Key features

Describe the key features of the PID approach and/or strategy

Since PIDs are a means to improve the quality and efficiency of research information, the working group approached this task by focusing on common use cases. The following use cases were considered and will be described one by one:

1. Registration and reporting research
2. Reusability and reproducibility of research
3. Evaluation and recognition of research
4. Grant application
5. Researcher profiling
6. Journal rankings

Key infrastructure

List and describe the key infrastructure (platforms, systems, services) that will activate this national PID approach and/or strategy

This list is to provide an impression of infrastructures that will be relevant to our national PID strategy at some point with respect to our use cases.

Name of infrastructure	Key purpose	List of integrated PIDs
SURFrepository	Repository	ORCID, Handle, DOI
ISAAC	Grant applications	n/a
NARCIS	National Academic Research and Collaborations Information System	URN:NBN, ORCID, Handle, DOI, ISNI, DAI, Ringgold
Pure	CRIS	
Converis	CRIS	
Metis	CRIS	

PIDs

List which functions and PIDs are identified in the strategy e.g. identification of research grants is a function and the PID recommended in the PID approach and/or strategy is CrossRef DOI

Function	PID type	Recommended or required?
Identification of researcher(s) for funding and reporting	ORCID	Recommended
Identification of research output for reporting	DOI, URN, ISSN, Handle	Recommended
Identification of organization	RoR, ISNI	Recommended
Identification of research grants	CrossRef DOI/GrantID	Recommended
Identification of research project	RAiD	Recommended
Identification of data set	Handle, DOI	Recommended
Identification of researcher(s) for findability research output	ORCID, ISNI or DAI	Recommended

Identification of research software	DOI, SWHID	Recommended
Identification of instruments	DOI, Handle, RRID, UID	Recommended
Identification of samples	IGSN, ARK, URN, HTTP URI (CETAF URI), DOI, UUID, RRID, BioSample accession number	Recommended

Impact and monitoring

Summarise any work to describe or track impact of the approach/strategy, including review and/or monitoring processes

Yet to be decided based on national action plan

Links

Include any links to relevant documents

[Towards a national PID roadmap | Zenodo](#)

[NWO Persistent Identifier Strategy | Zenodo](#)

[From ORCID Pilot to a PID-centric framework for Research Information | Zenodo](#)

Additional

Include any other relevant information

[Progress of measures to reduce pressure on the research system | NWO](#)

[Feasibility study Open Knowledge Base | Zenodo](#)

[An Open Knowledge Base for the Netherlands: Report of a Community Workshop | Zenodo](#)

Case Study - National PID Strategies New Zealand

Title	Case Study: PID Strategies in New Zealand
Creator(s)	Jason Gush (Programme Manager - ORCID; Royal Society Te Apārangī) https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8920-0452 jason.gush@royalsociety.org.nz Andrea Goethals (Programme Director, Preservation Research; NLNZ) https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5254-9818 andrea.goethals@dia.govt.nz
Date	29 June 2022

Features of National PID Approach and/or Strategy

Lead organisation(s)

The overarching strategy was derived as a consequence of the 2016 Research, Science and Innovation Domain Plan [5], which was developed in a process led by the Ministry of Business, Innovation and Employment (MBIE); Statistics New Zealand; the Ministry of Education; and the Tertiary Education Commission. In addition, this domain plan was endorsed by the other major organisations responsible for administering government research support, i.e., Callaghan Innovation, the Health Research Council of New Zealand, the Ministry for the Environment, the Ministry for Primary Resources, and Royal Society Te Apārangī. The domain plan represented a commitment from the NZ government and funding agencies to improve coordination of data and information and to lay the framework for developing a system-wide national research data infrastructure.

Another foundational document for ORCID was the Joint Statement of Principle: Adoption and use of ORCID identifiers in New Zealand (MBIE, MPI, MOE, TEC, Science NZ, Universities NZ, Independent Research Association of New Zealand (IRANZ), NZ Association of Scientists, HRC, Royal Society Te Apārangī) [2].

The ORCID strategy is implemented by lead agency Royal Society Te Apārangī, advised by a sector-representative Advisory Committee.

The DOI strategy is implemented by lead agency National Library of New Zealand, which is part of the Department of Internal Affairs.

Scope

The 'Research, Science and Innovation Domain Plan' [5] is intended to cover all research activity conducted in, or linked to, New Zealand.

The 'Joint Statement of Principle: Adoption and use of ORCID identifiers in New Zealand' [2] encourages the use of ORCID identifiers across the majority of the public research system, and commits signatories to supporting the use of the ORCID ID as the common researcher identifier in New Zealand.

For the NZ ORCID Consortium, membership is open to all NZ-based research organisations that are either: Government, Non-Profit, or IRANZ members, up to a limit of 99 members.

For the NZ DOI Consortium, membership is open to any New Zealand organisation as long as the organisation can:

- Provide and maintain at least the mandatory DataCite metadata elements for each item with a DOI.
- Make metadata openly available without restriction.
- Maintain a publicly accessible landing page for each item with a DOI.
- Ensure the DOI is updated as the landing page moves.

Drivers

Quality data and information informs strategic direction, sets investment priorities and improves business decision-making.

DOIs improve citation, track research impact, promote best practices in sharing research, develop a community for sharing experience and best practices.

ORCID IDs lower costs for both researchers and research administrators, improve workflows, and enable reuse and sharing of research related data.

Strategy development

Arguably, both the New Zealand ORCID and DOI consortia can claim to have their strategic origins in CONZUL (Council of NZ University Librarians, a committee of Universities New Zealand–Te Pōkai Tara) discussions and consultations undertaken in 2015-16.

Timeline for the DOI Consortium:

2015 - 2016 - CONZUL Working Group on Research Data Management was tasked to provide a framework on research data management. Some of the recommendations were that CONZUL member institutions “should adopt ORCID as a unique identifier of individuals and support national activity to enable this. CONZUL member institutions should adopt DataCite as a national data citation standard for research data objects and support national activity to enable this.” [4]

September 2017 - Report sponsored by CONZUL explored options for a Datacite service in New Zealand and recommended operating as a consortium of organisations

November 2018 - Series of meetings to discuss forming a Datacite DOI Consortium between representatives from University of Auckland, Canterbury University, data.govt.nz, ESR, Landcare Research, GNS, National Library of New Zealand, Statistics NZ. Various governance models for the Consortium were discussed. Ultimately members preferred a very light-weight structure.

January 2019 - Formation of the NZ DOI Consortium, led by National Library of New Zealand, with five initial member organisations

Timeline for the ORCID Consortium:

May 2015 - CONZUL agrees to form a joint working party with the Information and Communications Technology Committee (ICTC) to invite ORCID representatives to New Zealand.

September through November 2015 - ORCID in New Zealand scoping document presented to CONZUL/ICTC with a recommendation that CONZUL lobby MBIE to pursue an ORCID working group with a goal of national ORCID Consortium membership. MBIE hosts a roundtable discussion “Smart Research Information Systems for New Zealand” with ORCID Inc and sector representatives that leads to the formation of an ORCID Working Group (ORCID WG) to look at taking forward ORCID at a national level.

December 2015 - ORCID WG formed with representation from MBIE, the New Zealand Association of Scientists, Universities, Crown Research Institutes, research funders, and subsequently joined by a representative for IRANZ.

March 2016 - ORCID WG determines that all Universities, CRIs, and many IRANZ members and funders are interested in joining a national Consortium, and agrees that the Royal Society should be the lead agency. ORCID WG subgroup formed to draft a statement of principle for peak bodies and funders to endorse ORCID adoption. ORCID WG Technical subgroup formed to prepare Technical Requirements and recommendations for implementation in New Zealand.

April 2016 - MBIE agrees to provide financial support for the Consortium and lead agency role.

June 2016 - ORCID WG Technical subgroup reports back **[3]** with recommendation that a common web-based service be developed to remove technical and resource barriers to organisation participation.

July 2016 - Joint Statement of Principle: Adoption and use of ORCID identifiers in New Zealand published. **[1]**

June through September 2016 - ORCID WG and Royal Society recruit founding membership.

October 2016 - Formal launch of the New Zealand ORCID Consortium with the announcement of the 34 members (current membership 52).

June 2017 - Initial MVP of the NZ ORCID Hub launched (development completed late 2019).

Key features

A key feature for both Consortia was the emphasis on consortia approaches to lowering the costs for the many smaller organisations in New Zealand.

In addition, and at the time, for ORCID there was a perceived need to lower technical barriers to integrating with ORCID APIs which drove the decision to pursue development of the NZ ORCID Hub.

Key infrastructure

Name of infrastructure	Key purpose	List of integrated PIDs
NZ ORCID Hub https://orcidhub.org.nz/	Lower burdens of integration to enable all publicly funded NZ research organisations to participate	ORCID iD, RINGGOLD, GRID/ROR, DOI
DataCite tools and infrastructure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fabrica Web interface https://doi.datacite.org/ REST APIs https://support.datacite.org/docs/api 	Creation and management of DOIs; integration with data repository infrastructure; retrieve, query and browse DataCite DOI metadata records	DOI, ORCID iD, ROR ID
The New Zealand Research Information System (NZRIS) https://www.mbie.govt.nz/science-and-technology/science-and-innovation/research-and-data/nzris/	NZRIS will hold information about research funding and activity in New Zealand.	ORCID iD, NZBN, GRID/ROR, DOI, award and contract identifiers

PIDs

Function	PID type	Recommended or required?
Deduplication of researchers Linkage with awards Authoritative attribution of affiliation and works	ORCID iD	Recommended
Identification of datasets, software and other types of research outputs	DataCite DOI	Recommended
Identification of organisations	GRID/ROR	Recommended
Identification of organisations in NZRIS	NZBN	Required for data providers

Impact and monitoring

The NZ ORCID Consortium is operated by the Royal Society Te Apārangi as a Work Programme on behalf of MBIE. As a consequence, the activity comes with reporting and monitoring obligations, e.g., requirements for communications and timelines of support, secretariat support for the NZOC Advisory Committee, and other performance indicators such as the goal of 100% of members having an ORCID integration. In addition, the NZOC Advisory Committee set itself a goal of at least 80% of New Zealand's publicly-supported researchers having an ORCID iD; this target was reached June 2021 with ~83% of the NZ public research work force with an identifier, and this number continues to grow.

The NZ DOI Consortia does not currently use performance or other success indicators but will be looking to other DataCite DOI Consortia for potential models.

Links

[1] [Joint Statement of Principle: Adoption and use of ORCID identifiers in New Zealand](#) (2016)

[2] NZ ORCID Consortium Advisory Committee Terms of Reference
https://www.royalsociety.org.nz/assets/ToRJul2020_Jun2022-v2.pdf

[3] [New Zealand ORCID Working Group High-Level Technical Requirements Subgroup Report and Recommendations](#) (June 2016)

[4] [Research Data Management Framework Report](#) (2016)

[5] [Research, Science and Innovation Domain Plan](#) (2016)

Case Study - UK (RDA National PID Strategies Working Group)

Title	Case Study: National PID Strategy UK
Creator(s)	Christopher Brown, Product Manager, Jisc https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6884-9970 christopher.brown@jisc.ac.uk
Date	Original version – 7 February 2022 Revised - 3 May 2023

Features of National PID Strategy

Lead organisation(s)

List the lead organisation(s) and governance structure responsible for developing and/or maintaining the strategy

Organisations

Jisc - <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/>

UKRI - <https://www.ukri.org/>

Research England - <https://www.ukri.org/councils/research-england/>

Groups

Research Identifier National Coordination Committee - <https://rincc.org.uk/>

Scope

Define the scope of the strategy i.e. who it applies to

A national PID strategy applies across the academic research community. The work described in this case study is focused on UKRI/Research England funded PID work, led by Jisc, to develop a PID roadmap and strategy. The strategic goals were to include sector-wide cost savings through improved automation and technical integrations; wider adoption of persistent identifiers by institutions, funders, and individual researchers; and improved reporting mechanisms to better assess the impact of, and progress towards, an open access future. These offer value to funders, policy makers, institutions, researchers, and to commercial 'academia-adjacent' organisations.

Establishing a national community coordination and guidance group to guide and oversee work in this space, such as the Research Identifier National Coordinating Committee (RINCC), consisting of interested stakeholders (open research supporting organisations including funders, institutions, learned societies, infrastructure providers, and publishers), helps to liaise with PID providers, align integrations, and provide strategic oversight to these activities.

The development of a UK PID support network will support various stakeholders (particularly research information managers, funders, and content providers), in integrating PIDs within systems and adopting PID-enabled workflows.

Drivers

Describe the drivers behind the strategy development e.g. wanting to improve accuracy of research information, better track research impact, reduce administrative burden, etc.

The drivers behind a national PID strategy are the benefits and efficiencies it would bring to the whole research lifecycle through the adoption and integration of priority PIDs in the systems and workflows that make up the digital research environment. The benefits of widespread PID adoption include better workflows and automation for researchers, funders, research organisations, and end-users. The impact would result in cost savings and improved reporting mechanisms that would enable assessment of such impact. Improvements and efficiencies, for the benefit of all stakeholders, can only be achieved through widespread PID adoption.

A graphical representation of the benefits of the five priority PIDs at each stage of a typical research lifecycle including grant application, output publication, and research reporting and evaluation is shown in Appendix A of the UK PID Consortium: Cost-Benefit Analysis report [1]. The text from this diagram is shown in the following table:

STAGE	Description	PIDs	Benefits
GRANT APPLICATION	Researchers and institutions pass PIDs for previous grants, outputs, organisations, people, and projects to grant application systems	DOI ORCID ROR RAiD	1) Less manual data entry 2) More accurate data 3) More time for including contextual information
GRANT APPLICATION AND REVIEW	Funders ingest data about grants, outputs, organisations, and projects from PID registries	DOI ORCID ROR RAiD	1) Less manual data entry 2) More accurate data 3) More time for including contextual information 4) Easier reviewer selection and recognition
GRANT AWARD	Funders register DOIs for new grant metadata	DOI	1) Globally unique grant IDs and metadata to aid reporting 2) Authoritative metadata and connections to other PIDs to aid

			project management 3) Simplified communication of and compliance with policies (e.g. OA, DMPs, etc.)
GRANT AWARD	Institutions ingest data about grants and associated people and organisations	DOI ORCID ROR	1) More accurate data 2) Time/effort savings 3) Improved reporting
PROJECT REGISTRATION	Institutions register RAiDs for projects and add/update links to associated grants, equipment, people, and organisations	DOI ORCID ROR RAiD	1) More accurate data 2) Time/effort savings 3) Improved visibility of collaborations across institutions and countries
OUTPUT SUBMISSION	Researchers share their ORCID iD when submitting new outputs and connect to ROR IDs for institutional affiliations and grant DOIs for funding	DOI ORCID ROR	1) More accurate data about co-authors, affiliations, and funding 2) Time/effort savings in review and metadata creation 3) Easier sign-in 4) Easier APC management 5) Easier reviewer selection and recognition
OUTPUT PUBLICATION	Publisher/repositories ingest data about grants, people, projects, and organisations linked to outputs	DOI ORCID ROR RAiD	1) Reduced administrative overhead for publishers 2) Improved author experience 3) Richer metadata to aid discovery, analysis, and reporting
OUTPUT REGISTRATION	Publishers/repositories register DOIs for new outputs and populate metadata	DOI	1) Globally unique output IDs and metadata to aid analysis, citation, discovery, and reporting 2) Embedded PIDs for associated entities (authors, funding, etc.) streamline reporting and analysis 3) Greater ability to track reach and impact of content
CONTENT NOTIFICATIONS	PID registries send automatic updates of new publications etc. to institutions and funders	DOI ORCID	1) Reduced administrative overhead for institutions/funders 2) More timely data for reporting and analysis 3) Less manual data entry 4) More accurate data 5) Time/effort savings for researchers

REPORTING	Researchers and institutions pass PIDs for outputs, organisations, people, and projects to funders' reporting systems	DOI ORCID ROR RAiD	1) Less manual data entry 2) More accurate data 3) More time for including contextual information
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Strategy development

Describe the process and timeline through which the strategy was developed e.g. Advisory Group was formed led by a government agency, there was a consultation period in which xx people and organisations were involved, the process by which agreement was achieved etc.

Project timeline

June 2018 – Tickell’s Open Access to Research Publications [2] The Universities UK Open Access Coordination Group, chaired by Professor Adam Tickell, recommended the use, and in some cases mandating, of PIDs. One of its recommendations was for “Jisc to lead on selecting and promoting a range of unique identifiers, including ORCID, in collaboration with sector leaders with relevant partner organisations. Funders of research to consider mandating the use of an agreed range of unique identifiers as a condition of grant.”

July 2019 – PID Roadmap report [3] Funded by Research England and commissioned by Jisc. A consultation workshop, run by Jisc and independent consultants, was run with 39 attendees made up of funders, infrastructure providers, publishers (both open access and subscription), research institutions, scholarly societies, and system vendors. The findings of the workshop were validated by consultation with a broad community of experts. Identified five priority PIDs and proposed the outline of a national PID strategy.

December 2019 – UK PIDs for OA project starts Funded by Research England and administered by Jisc. The aim was to develop a national PID strategy coordinated across the academic research community. Strategic goals included sector-wide cost savings through improved automation and technical integrations; wider adoption of persistent identifiers by institutions, funders, and individual researchers; and improved reporting mechanisms to better assess the impact of, and progress towards, an open access future. Its key tasks were to 1) create a roadmap to implement the strategy; 2) explore barriers and opportunities for PID adoption in the UK; and 3) build a community around the strategy.

May/June 2020 – Focus groups [4] Part of the UK PIDs for OA project. Consisted of 28 participants from 19 organisations in five focus groups. The objectives of the focus groups were to take a deep dive into specific community issues, explore perceptions and elucidate needs; validate the selection of five priority PIDs and the approach of a national PID support consortium; refine and prioritise the interventions outlined in the roadmap report[3]. The findings were that there are major sector requirements around education and support. Emphasised the need for leadership and strong governance, that is, it is important to get questions of persistent

identifiers into high level national strategic discussions and to develop governance and sustainability models that allow for long term community engagement.

August 2020 – PID adoption survey [5] Part of the UK PIDs for OA project. The survey gathered 93 responses, 75% of which were from organisations which primarily serve a UK audience. Researchers were overwhelmingly the focus of organisations responding. Its major findings were: Support for the project’s focus on five ‘priority PIDs’ for open research, with DOIs for outputs and ORCID iDs for people being both widely known and adopted; Technical barriers and costs of PID adoption are seen as too high; The value proposition for PIDs is not understood.

October 2020 - Consortium Task Group Part of the UK PIDs for OA project. Chaired by UKRI, the group explored the value propositions for PIDs, and the potential role of an extended national consortium in driving adoption and increasing coverage. The group found that there was a good case for a consortium, if it was focused on support for PID integration, and recommended a robust cost-benefit analysis before further work was done. UK "multi-PID consortium" business case [6] prepared for the Consortium Task Group - November 2020 and revised January 2021.

December 2020 – Research Identifier National Coordinating Committee (RINCC) [7] [8] At the final UK PIDs for OA project stakeholder group meeting, there was overwhelming support for ongoing coordination via the RINCC. This was established to focus on governance and community accountability. Consisting of interested stakeholders, the group was recommended to liaise with PID providers, align integrations, and provide strategic oversight to these activities. Membership is made up of a majority of open research supporting organisations including funders, institutions, learned societies, infrastructure providers, and publishers.

March 2021 – UK PIDs for OA project ends. “Phase 2” starts The Jisc led, Research England funded project ends but further funding supports follow-on work to build a business case for investment in PIDS. Phase 2 of the project focused on communication and community development (building a community development strategy that will establish and operationalise the RINCC), and PID-optimised workflow development (developing “PID optimised” workflows for 1) Funding awards, from application to reporting and evaluation; 2) Institutional research management; 3) Research article publication; and 4) Research data management and publication)). In addition, the development of a UK PID support consortium to support stakeholders, particularly research information managers, funders, and content providers, in integrating with PIDs and adopting PID-enabled workflows.

June 2021 - Publication of the cost-benefit analysis report [1] and the first meeting of the RINCC Meeting co-chaired by Jisc and the British Library. Presentation of cost benefit analysis report [1] and proposal for a ‘multi-PID’ support consortium.

August 2021 - UKRI’s open access policy [9] calls for the extensive use of PIDs for journals, articles, authors, grants, funders, organisations, and projects.

November 2021 - Second meeting of the RINCC and case for investment in a national PID strategy Meeting co-chaired by Jisc and the British Library. Presented the case for investment in a UK persistent identifier strategy [10]. This calls for a national investment in activities to implement PIDs in alignment with the UK's strategic needs.

June 2022 to November 2022 UK PIDs for OA project “Phase 3” Funding from UKRI-STFC on digital infrastructure developments supported the following third phase of work: Business planning and roadmap to establish a dedicated team of technical, educational, and communications specialists hosted at a trusted UK institution to drive forward the PID agenda through the PID Support Network (previously referred to as the multi-PID support consortium); Business planning and roadmap for a UK RAiD Registration Agency; supporting RAiD pathfinder projects.

July 2022 – Tickell’s Independent review of research bureaucracy report [11] endorses the proposal for a PID Support Network and recommends extending this model to other facets of digital research platforms as appropriate and recommends that Jisc, as the designated umbrella body for digital services and solutions in the UK, should take a leading role in co-ordinating this activity for the higher education sector.

September 2022 – PID optimised workflows published [12]. The workflows show a vision of a more efficient future where PIDs are used throughout the research lifecycle to enable automation, efficiency, new discovery tools, and analysis. Following community discussions and a survey, they were selected based on where the community felt increased use of PIDs would have the greatest impact. These are 1) Funding awards, from application to reporting and evaluation; 2) Institutional research management; 3) Research article publication; and 4) Research data management and publication.

November 2022 – Revised version of the cost-benefit analysis report [13]

As part of the third phase of work mentioned above, a revised version of the cost-benefit analysis report is published, with a number of methodological improvements and updated data.

November 2022 - Third meeting of the RINCC and case for investment in a national PID strategy Meeting co-chaired by Jisc and the British Library. Presented the business case and roadmap for a PID Support Network and a RAiD Registration Agency. The Terms of Reference [8] were agreed and a volunteer third co-chair from the University of Oxford was selected. Meetings to continue with a target of two meetings a year and increasing membership.

Next steps – Continue work to establish a PID Support Network and a RAiD Registration Agency (including supporting RAiD pathfinder projects).

The Jisc webpage “**A national persistent identifier research strategy**” [14] describes all the work listed in this timeline. It will continue to be updated to reflect the progress of the PID research strategy.

Key features

Describe the key features of the strategy

Selection of priority PIDS

The following priority PIDs were selected:

- Crossref Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for funding grants of all kinds
- Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier (ORCID) iDs for people
- Research Activity Identifiers (RAiDs) for projects
- Research Organization Registry (ROR) identifiers for organisations
- Crossref and DataCite Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for outputs (especially articles and data)

Clear arguments for why such an investment is needed

- PIDs are required to deliver a range of policy priorities and can help to align and join up work across the drive to deliver them
- PIDs have the power to save time and money and boost the return on investments in research
- PIDs provide a means for the UK to maintain its competitive advantage in the hyper-connected global research landscape
- The power of information systems has been vital in bringing the UK through a number of recent crises. The resilience of the UK's knowledge economy is clearly dependent on the resilience of these systems, and PIDs provide a means of strengthening these systems against future shocks and the risk of information loss
- In an age of global research collaboration, open, sustainable, international information systems are vital both for the trustworthiness of our research network and for our ability to analyse and adapt strategically

Governance

The Research Identifier National Coordinating Committee (RINCC) has been established to provide strategic oversight and international coordination for the future of PID activities in the UK. Its combined membership covers the majority of open research-supporting organisations in the UK. Its role is to provide strategic oversight, troubleshoot barriers, provide national and international leadership, and participate in evolving business models, forming consortia, and support PID strategy initiatives.

Support

There is both a need and a strong business case for investment in a PID support framework for the UK research and innovation sector. A PID support network (previously referred to as a multi-PID support consortium) would help drive PID adoption and coverage to levels that would deliver value. Without comprehensive adoption and use of PIDs, organisations large and small will be disadvantaged in the modern, digital-first, research environment.

Leadership

A costed set of interventions have been identified, which should take the UK PID agenda to a sustainable, self-supporting level, capable of delivering the wider goals of a range of policy priorities for the UK. The implementation of a national PID strategy requires strategic leadership and vision from major funders and key stakeholders. This is required to drive change, and adoption and implementation, across the research sector. Without it the benefits cannot be realised.

Funding

UKRI, Research England, Jisc, and the many stakeholders who have participated in the programme, whether in research, task forces or the RINCC, have all invested significant amounts (in time, effort and resources) in bringing the roadmap to its current stage. The return on all these investments will decay without a timely, targeted follow-up investment to unlock and deliver the benefits outlined in the strategic case [10] and in the cost-benefit analysis report [1].

Business case

The business case for investment in a UK persistent identifier strategy [10] calls for a national investment in activities to implement PIDs in alignment with the UK's strategic needs. The steps necessary are:

1. Create a consortial network to lower barriers to and costs of PID adoption
2. Community education and promotion to drive adoption of PIDs to leverage network effects
3. Understand critical information pathways between funders, institutions, and content publishers
4. Establish technical and social requirements for systematic exchange and reuse of information across stakeholder groups

Three components are necessary to deliver these needs:

1. National access to and support for key PIDs
2. A national coordination body to guide and oversee work in this space
3. A dedicated team of technical, educational, and communications specialists hosted at a trusted UK institution to drive forward the PID agenda.

Key infrastructure

List and describe the key infrastructure (platforms, systems, services) that will activate this national PID strategy

Name of infrastructure	Key purpose	List of integrated PIDs
UK ORCID Consortium	Jisc is the lead organisation for this service providing reduced cost and support for its members	ORCID

DataCite Consortium	The British Library is the UK consortium and works with organisations in the UK and Ireland to ensure that their data, software and other research items can be uniquely identified with DOIs	DOI
RAiD	A Persistent Identifier for research projects. Plans for a Registration Agency in the UK with the Registration Authority run by the Australian Research Data Commons	RAiDs for projects
UKRI New Funding Service (replacing Je-S from January 2024)	Grant application service	Various TBC

PIDs

List which functions and PIDs are identified in the strategy e.g. identification of research grants is a function and the PID recommended in the strategy is Crossref DOI

Function	PID type	Recommended or required?
People	ORCID	Recommended
Outputs	Crossref and DataCite DOIs	Recommended
Grants	Crossref DOIs	Recommended
Organisations	ROR identifiers	Recommended
Projects	RAiDs (Research Activity IDs)	Recommended

Impact and monitoring

Summarise any work to describe or track impact of the strategy, including review and/or monitoring processes

The UK PIDs for Open Access project (and subsequent follow on work) has helped to define a national PID strategy in the UK and increase adoption of PIDs to support open access. This work has had the following impact:

- Better understanding of the state of the art and best practice in the governance and delivery of PID services
- Increased awareness of persistent identifiers across the research sector
- Five validated priority PIDs selected through community consultation - outputs (DOIs), grants (Crossref Grant ID), people (ORCID), project (RAiD), organisations (ROR)
- Address inefficiencies and administrative burden in Open Access and publication workflows

Tracking the impact of a national strategy requires ownership from major stakeholders, in particular funders, and governance structures to be put in place. The RINCC has been established to provide governance and community accountability. The purpose of the RINCC is set out in its Terms of Reference[8]:

“The UK’s Research Identifier National Coordinating Committee (RINCC) will support the sustainability and growth of priority persistent identifier (PID) systems, helping to identify and deliver key integrations of PID services and associated metadata for the UK research ecosystem, with a focus on tangible, quantifiable benefits. As a national group, the RINCC will collate and reflect the needs of all UK stakeholders in open research on the global stage, via a coherent national strategy for fair, reliable, and accessible PID adoption.”

Links

Include any links to strategy documents

[1] Brown, Josh; Jones, Phill; Meadows, Alice; Murphy, Fiona; & Clayton, Paul. (2021). UK PID Consortium: Cost-Benefit Analysis (1.0). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4772627>

[2] Tickell, A. (2018) Open Access to Research Publications: Independent advice. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/774956/Open-access-to-research-publications-2018.pdf

[3] Brown, Josh (2020) Developing a persistent identifier roadmap for open access to UK research. <https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/7840/>

[4] Murphy, Fiona and Jones, Phill (2020) Jisc PID Agency: Focus Group Report. <https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/8166/>

[5] Brown, Josh and Meadows, Alice (2020) Persistent identifiers adoption and awareness survey report. <https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/8107/>

[6] Brown, Josh and Meadows, Alice (2021). UK "multi-PID consortium" business case. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4760886>

[7] Research Identifier National Coordinating Committee (RINCC) <https://rincc.org.uk/>

[8] RINCC terms of reference <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1-TYRAFBIF5207ugs1xJfc7saasU7o-dfi66qjZ8rmZA/edit?usp=sharing>

[9] UKRI Open Access Policy (2021). See especially Annex 2: Technical requirements for research articles. <https://www.ukri.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/UKRI-180821-UKRIOpenAccessPolicy-2.pdf>

[10] Brown, Josh; Jones, Phill; Meadows, Alice; Murphy, Fiona (2022) The case for investment in a UK persistent identifier strategy <https://zenodo.org/record/6012367#.YgKnQPinxEY>

[11] Tickell, A. Independent review of research bureaucracy – Final Report https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1094648/independent-review-research-bureaucracy-final-report.pdf

[12] Brown, Josh, Jones, Phill, Meadows, Alice, & Murphy, Fiona. (2022, September 16). PID-optimised workflows: A vision of a more efficient future. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7085489> and webpage - <https://www.morebrains.coop/jisc-pid-workflows/>

[13] Brown, Josh; Jones, Phill; Meadows, Alice; Murphy, Fiona (2022) Revised cost-benefit analysis for the UK PID Support Network <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7356219>

[14] Jisc's "A national persistent identifier research strategy" webpage <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/rd/projects/a-national-persistent-identifier-research-strategy>

Additional

Include any other relevant information

The following are not referenced in the case study but are relevant to the UK PID strategy work.

[15] Research Data Alliance national PID strategies working group. <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/national-pid-strategies-wg>

[16] Meadows, Alice (2020) Blog post: There's A PID For That! Next Steps in Establishing a National PID Strategy <https://scholarlycommunications.jiscinvolve.org/wp/2020/10/09/theres-a-pid-for-that-next-steps-in-establishing-a-national-pid-strategy/>

[17] Meadows, Alice & Jones, Phill (2021) Blog post: Why Publishers Should Care About Persistent Identifiers <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2021/06/21/why-publishers-should-care-about-persistent-identifiers/>

[18] Meadows, Alice & Jones, Phill (2021) Blog post: Making the Case for a PID-Optimized World <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2021/06/22/making-the-case-for-a-pid-optimized-world/>

[19] Brown, Christopher; Brown, Josh (2021) (presentation): Positive People Present their Persistent Pursuit of Practically Perfect PID Partnerships at PIDapalooza <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4475520>

[20] Brown, Christopher; Brown, Josh (2021) (presentation): National PID Strategies - UK <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4748422>

[21] Brown, Christopher (2021) (presentation): National PID Strategies Working Group - UK update <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5752200>

[22] Brown, Christopher (2022) (presentation): National PID Strategies Working Group - UK case study <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6840808>

[23] Meadows, Alice (2023) Blog post: Why PID Strategies Are Having A Moment - And Why You Should Care <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2023/01/25/why-pid-strategies-are-having-a-moment-and-why-you-should-care/>